

JANUARY 05 2026

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J. Acoust. Soc. Am. 159, 117–140 (2026)

<https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0042017>

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Perceptual compensation of the reproduction room for single-source Ambisonics recordings

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ABSTRACT:

Ambisonics is a method for capturing and rendering a sound field accurately, assuming that the acoustics of the playback room does not significantly influence the sound field. However, in practice, the acoustics of the playback room may lead to a noticeable degradation in sound quality. This paper proposes a recording and rendering method based on Ambisonics that utilizes a perceptually motivated approach to compensate for the reverberation of the playback room. The recorded direct and reverberant sound field components in the spherical harmonics domain are spectrally and spatially compensated to preserve the relevant auditory cues, including the direction of arrival of the direct sound, the spectral energy of the direct and reverberant sound components, and the interaural coherence across each auditory band. In contrast to the conventional Ambisonics, a flexible number of Ambisonics channels can be used for audio rendering. Listening test results show that the proposed method provides a perceptually accurate rendering of the originally recorded sound field, outperforming both conventional Ambisonics without compensation and even Ambisonics reproduction in a simulated anechoic room. Additionally, perceptual evaluations of listeners seated at the center of the loudspeaker array demonstrate that the method remains robust to head rotation and minor displacements.

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(Received 26 July 2025; revised 8 December 2025; accepted 9 December 2025; published online 5 January 2026)

[Editor: Ning Xiang]

Pages: 117–140

I. INTRODUCTION

An objective of an audio rendering system is to capture an acoustic scene, such as a concert hall performance, and reproduce it in another room in a way that listeners in the playback room perceive the sound field as closely matching the original performance. Theoretically, methods such as wave field synthesis (WFS) (Berkhout, 1988) and Ambisonics (Gerzon, 1973; Daniel, 2000), allow for the perfect reproduction of a recorded sound field. However, both methods have a limitation where the reproduction room ideally needs to have boundaries that are free of reflections. In addition, spacing of loudspeakers must be very dense in order to avoid spatial aliasing effects. In practice, distortions arising from the use of a limited number of loudspeakers and reverberation in the playback room can significantly reduce the accuracy of sound field reproduction. Additionally, loudspeakers typically exhibit non-flat high-frequency responses in the off-axis direction, which can be crucial for the reverberant sound field. Reproduction of a recorded reverberant sound field on loudspeakers that are themselves placed in a reverberant playback environment is known as room-in-room (RinR) sound reproduction, which has been discussed to alter the perceived sound field by introducing additional reflections, reverberation, and potential coloration, thereby distorting the accuracy

of the original recording and reducing spatial fidelity (Haeussler and van de Par, 2019). Additionally, most currently available recording microphones support only up to 4th- or 6th-order Ambisonics (mh acoustics, 2023, 2025). At these orders, accurate sound-field reconstruction in the high-frequency range is confined to a small area, referred to as the sweet spot (Ahrens and Spors, 2009). As a rule of thumb, the sweet spot extends up to about 650 Hz per Ambisonics order for a head-sized radius (e.g., ~650 Hz for 1st order, ~1.3 kHz for 2nd order, and ~2.6 kHz for 4th order).

In the domain of WFS, various approaches have been developed to compensate for the effects of the reproduction room. A method based on WFS theory and plane wave decomposition was proposed to compensate for the room reflection over a large area by synthesizing the desired sound field while explicitly modeling and canceling the effects of early reflections (Spors *et al.*, 2003). Adaptive wave field synthesis (AWFS) methods (Gauthier and Berry, 2006; Stefanakis *et al.*, 2010) and similar approaches treat dereverberation as an inverse problem, aiming to equalize the playback system's transfer function at multiple points in order to minimize reproduction errors at these control positions. However, such multi-point sampling and equalization methods can lead to poor equalization at positions outside the control points (Fielder, 2001).

In the Ambisonics domain, hardware solutions exist to control the reverberant field, such as using directive

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loudspeakers to reduce the energy of reflections (Poletti *et al.*, 2010). A method for two-dimensional room equalization over an extended area, employing cylindrical harmonics to model room reflections, has been proposed (Betlehem and Abhayapala, 2005). However, a drawback of this system is the need for a very large number of equalization filters. A modified version of this method for three-dimensional (3D) space was introduced (Lecomte *et al.*, 2018). In contrast to the approach in Bethlehem and Abhayapala (2005), this method introduces a new filtering matrix that reduces the number of equalization filters and simplifies the matrix inversion process. In multizone reproduction systems, intensity-matching techniques have been proposed to align the energy-flux direction of the reproduced field with the desired direction, thereby enhancing spatial cues across larger listening areas (Zuo *et al.*, 2021).

Although inverse filtering could in principle be applied to compensate the playback chain, it is rarely practical in Ambisonics reproduction because of robustness issues and its sensitivity to listener position and room acoustics, which can undermine its effectiveness (Bäumer *et al.*, 2025). The inverse filtering also carries the risk of amplifying noise and errors, particularly at higher frequencies due to measurement inaccuracies (Zhang *et al.*, 2008; Bäumer *et al.*, 2025). Computational complexity also adds to the difficulty, as creating and implementing real-time filters for high-order systems requires significant resources (Hold *et al.*, 2024). Moreover, listener movement outside the calibrated area or in dynamic environments can make the filtering ineffective (Mouchtaris *et al.*, 2000). Furthermore, inverse filtering may introduce perceptual artifacts, such as overcorrection, resulting in the reproduction of an unnatural sound field that undermines the immersive experience (Norcross *et al.*, 2004). Finally, these methods cannot compensate for the inherent problems in low-order Ambisonics recording and reproduction (Moreau *et al.*, 2006).

Complementary to physically based methods like WFS and Ambisonics, perceptually motivated approaches focus on delivering a perceptually accurate sound experience, even if the exact sound field is not precisely recreated. Ambisonics playback can also be interpreted perceptually as a panning method, similar to vector base amplitude panning (VBAP), which effectively enlarges the listening area (Stitt *et al.*, 2014; Zotter and Frank, 2017). It is important to note, however, that the encoding stage of spherical microphone recordings must remain physically accurate (Zotter and Frank, 2019). Another different approach is directional audio coding (DirAC) (Pulkki, 2007), which decomposes sound into directional and spatially diffuse components based on a diffuseness criterion in the time-frequency domain. These components are then processed and reproduced through separate signal paths. The direct sound, retaining its directional cues, is estimated in short time frames per frequency band and rendered using the VBAP method (Pulkki, 1997). Parallel to that, the diffuse sound is rendered through multiple loudspeakers using decorrelation techniques to create a realistic, spatially diffuse sound field. Moreover, a modified version of DirAC has been proposed, utilizing higher-order microphone arrays recordings to

be able to better extract multiple simultaneous sound sources (Politis *et al.*, 2015). The DirAC approach does not account for the reverberation of the reproduction room.

Instead of suppressing the reverberation of the playback room using inverse filtering, which leads to robustness issues and practical challenges with inverse filtering, a method for recording and rendering was proposed in Grosse and van de Par (2015) that perceptually compensates for the effects of the playback room. In this approach, a near-source microphone is used to capture the direct sound, while two distant microphones are employed to record the reverberant sound. The processed direct sound is then reproduced using two loudspeakers positioned in front of the listener. The processed reverberant sound is reproduced using two distant dipole loudspeakers, oriented so that their directional patterns predominantly point away from the listener, with the aim of acoustically only exciting the reverberant sound field without creating noticeable direct sound-path components. A perceptually motivated optimization procedure is employed, where the energies of the direct and reverberant sounds are separately compensated in each frequency band. This is achieved by equalizing the reproduced RinR impulse responses to ensure they match for the listener in both the recording and playback rooms. The optimization process also involves compensating for interaural coherence (IC) (Faller and Merimaa, 2004) between the left and right ear signals to preserve the perceived spatial diffuseness of the sound field in the reproduction room. To design the compensation filters, a dummy head is placed in the recording room as a reference, while another dummy head is situated in the playback room for optimization purposes. By incorporating the playback room in the optimization process, the acoustics of the playback room is perceptually compensated.

Relatively few studies in the literature address compensating for the reverberation of playback rooms in the Ambisonics domain. This study proposes a perceptually motivated compensation method in the Ambisonics domain, inspired by the primary approach in Grosse and van de Par (2015). However, instead of using distributed microphones, a conventional Ambisonics recording is employed using a single spherical microphone placed at the listener position. In the proposed method, the direct and reverberant components are separated after recording and then perceptually compensated and reproduced through separate signal paths.

The paper is organized as follows: Sec. II explains the recording and reproduction of conventional Ambisonics, Section III describes the proposed approach, Sec. IV describes the optimization procedure, and Sec. V presents an evaluation of the algorithm. Section VI is the Discussion, and finally, Sec. VII concludes the paper, including suggestions for future work.

II. RECORDING AND REPRODUCTION OF CONVENTIONAL AMBISONICS

This section explains the signal representation in the Ambisonics domain, the recording and encoding, and the decoding and reproduction.

A. Sound field representation

Here, the precise definitions will be given such as used in this paper for representing spherical harmonics (SH). SH of order n and degree m (Daniel, 2000) are defined as follows:

$$Y_n^m(\theta, \varphi) \equiv \sqrt{\frac{(2n+1)(n-|m|)!}{4\pi(n+|m|)!}} P_{n,|m|}(\cos\theta) \times \begin{cases} \sqrt{2} \sin(|m|\varphi) & \text{if } m < 0, \\ 1 & \text{if } m = 0, \\ \sqrt{2} \cos(|m|\varphi) & \text{if } m > 0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where θ and φ represent elevation and azimuth angles, respectively, and $P_{n,m}$ denotes the associated Legendre polynomial of order n and degree m . Note that this definition does not include the Condon–Shortley phase (Arfken et al., 2011). The SH expansion of a plane wave arriving from incidence angle (θ_s, φ_s) is given by

$$e^{jkr} = 4\pi \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n j^n j_n(kr) Y_n^m(\theta_s, \varphi_s) Y_n^m(\theta, \varphi), \quad (2)$$

where j is the imaginary unit number, k is the wavenumber, and $j_n(kr)$ is the n th-order spherical Bessel function of the first kind. The SH expansion for a point source at position $\mathbf{r}_s = (r_s, \theta_s, \varphi_s)$ with $r < r_s$ is given by

$$\frac{e^{jk\|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_s\|}}{4\pi\|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_s\|} = -jk \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n h_n^{(2)}(kr_s) j_n(kr) \times Y_n^m(\theta_s, \varphi_s) Y_n^m(\theta, \varphi), \quad (3)$$

where $h_n^{(2)}$ is the spherical Hankel function of the second kind and of order n . In practice, the infinite summation across n in Eq. (3) is truncated to a finite order N .

B. Recording and encoding

A general form of the SH expansion of the recorded pressure by a microphone in a room is given by

$$P(r, \theta, \varphi, k) = \sum_{n=0}^N \sum_{m=-n}^n b_n(kr) A_n^m(k) Y_n^m(\theta, \varphi), \quad (4)$$

where $b_n(kr)$ is the radial term that depends on the scattering characteristics of the recording point, and $A_n^m(k)$ are the SH coefficients. The recorded pressure $P(r, \theta, \varphi, k)$ is assumed to be the summation of the direct and reverberant sounds, which can be modeled by plane waves or point sources. The spatial information of both the direct and reverberant sounds is summed in the SH coefficient $A_n^m(k)$.

This study will only consider the capturing of a single source. Although, theoretically a single source, including room acoustics can be perfectly represented in the spherical domain, in practice, the maximum order of available Ambisonics recording microphones is limited to typically

four (mh acoustics, 2023) or six (mh acoustics, 2025). We use the EM-32 Eigenmike microphone from mh acoustics (Summit, NJ) (mh acoustics, 2023) with a rigid sphere for sound recording, which supports 4th-order Ambisonics ($N=4$). The radial term $b_n(kr)$ in Eq. (4) describes the scattering behavior of a rigid spherical microphone array with radius r_e . For such an array, the terms are given by

$$b_n(kr) = j_n(kr) - \frac{j_n'(kr_e)}{h_n^{(2)'}(kr_e)} h_n^{(2)}(kr). \quad (5)$$

This radial term is not part of the SH themselves and must be compensated using frequency-dependent radial filters in order to obtain accurate Ambisonics signals. The SH coefficients are obtained from the recorded pressure of microphone capsules on a spherical microphone array,

$$A_n^m(k) = \frac{\sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_q P(r_e, \theta_q, \varphi_q, k) Y_n^m(\theta_q, \varphi_q)}{b_n(kr_e)}, \quad (6)$$

in which r_e is the radius of microphone array, θ_q and φ_q are respectively the elevation and azimuth angles of microphone capsules on the rigid sphere, Q is the number of microphone capsules (equal to 32 for EM32) on the array, and α_q are element weights used to maintain the orthonormality of SH in order to achieve limited discrete sampling of theoretically continuous spatial recordings (Rafaely, 2015). The EM32 microphone signals are encoded into 4th-order Ambisonics using the Eigenmike signal processing software “EigenStudio.” This software performs the SH decomposition of the 32 microphone channels and applies the required frequency-dependent radial filters to compensate for the rigid-sphere scattering of the array. Consequently, no additional radial filtering was necessary in our processing pipeline. The SH components $A_n^m(k)$ derived from the Eigenmike in the time domain are referred to as “Eigenbeams.” We use the term Eigenbeam to remain consistent with the manufacturer’s EM32 documentation. In this study, 25 Eigenbeams were used directly as provided by the EM32 processing. Remaining within the low-order Ambisonics domain can lead to significant issues, including spatial aliasing and poor low-frequency estimation during recording (Moreau et al., 2006). At low frequencies, capturing higher-order Ambisonics (HOA) is particularly challenging because the Ambisonics signals often fall into the noise floor. For that reason, reproduction at low frequencies is limited to lower-order Ambisonics. Consequently, playback using conventional Ambisonics suffers from limited spatial resolution at low frequencies, where the dominant limitation is the array’s self-noise. The cutoff frequencies of the Eigenbeams are summarized in Table I.

C. Decoding and reproduction

A spherical loudspeaker array was employed using a 50-node Lebedev grid, which supports reproduction up to

TABLE I. Cutoff frequencies for Eigenbeams's orders (mh acoustics, 2023).

Eigenbeam order, n	Approximate cutoff frequency (Hz)
0, 1	30
2	400
3	1000
4	1800

5th order. The 50-node Lebedev grid has been shown to outperform Fliege and t-design grids of similar size in terms of harmonic orthonormality errors and spatial aliasing when used for sound field reproduction (Lecomte et al., 2016).

For decoding of the 4th-order Eigenmike recordings (Eigenbeam components $A_{25 \times 1}$), we applied the simple source formulation (Poletti et al., 2010; Lecomte et al., 2016). In the frequency domain, the decoder takes the form

$$d_{spk} = GYA, \tag{7}$$

where $Y_{50 \times 25}$ is the spherical harmonic matrix evaluated at the loudspeaker positions and $G_{50 \times 50}$ is a diagonal matrix of quadrature weights to preserve the orthonormality of the column of $Y_{50 \times 25}$. The quadrature weights $G_{50 \times 50}$ correspond to non-uniform loudspeaker gains that preserve the orthonormality of the reproduced Ambisonics components for the Lebedev grid. Node positions and weights are given in Lecomte et al. (2016). It should be mentioned that no near-field compensation (NFC) term dependent on the radius

of loudspeaker array (r_{spk}) is included in the decoder. Although NFC is commonly introduced in theoretical Ambisonics formulations through the form

$$F_{spk}^{-1} = \frac{1}{-jkh_n^{(2)}(kr_{spk})}, \tag{8}$$

an analysis of these filters in relation to the cutoff frequencies of the Eigenmike channels listed in Table I shows that the frequency region in which NFC would have an influence lies entirely outside the operational passband used in this study. In addition, NFC has negligible effect at low Ambisonics orders and is only relevant at very low frequencies below approximately $n \times 36$ Hz for a loudspeaker array with a radius of 1.5 m. NFC further assumes near-field source conditions and an ideal spherical loudspeaker layout, assumptions that do not hold in our reproduction setup, so NFC was omitted. For conventional Ambisonics decoding, Eq. (7) was used directly with the Eigenbeam input signals.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

The main idea is illustrated in Fig. 1. As can be seen, the spatial sound field is captured in the recording venue using a rigid spherical microphone array. This allows the use of SH representations for optimizing the rendering. To overcome common limitations of Ambisonics at high frequencies and to mitigate the detrimental effects of playback

FIG. 1. A block diagram of the proposed approach. The sound is first recorded using a spherical microphone array and then separated into two processing paths. The direct-sound path (blue-color branch) is extracted by beamforming and mapped onto three VBAP loudspeakers with the corresponding panning gains G_{vbap} . It is then processed using Gammatone filterbank analysis, where frequency-dependent gains $g_{dir}^{(i)}$ are applied to optimize the energy of the reproduced direct sound before playback. The reverberant-sound path (green-color branch) uses all Ambisonics channels up to 4th order for reproduction via the loudspeaker array. These channels are weighted with the vector $M_{wxyzR}^{(j)}$, and after Gammatone-based energy compensation with gains $g_{rev}^{(i)}$, they are rendered conventionally through Ambisonics decoding. For optimization, auditory transfer functions (ATFs) derived from BRIRs of two dummy heads in the recording and playback rooms are used as references and targets.

acoustics, the direct sound field components and the remaining diffuse sound field are first separated using beamforming techniques. This will allow a number of the limitations of conventional Ambisonics to be overcome. In Ambisonics-based sound reproduction, rendering high frequencies introduces a significant challenge due to the limited size of the sweet spot. Furthermore, the acoustic characteristics of the reproduction environment must be carefully compensated to ensure accurate spatial audio rendering.

Inverse filtering methods in the Ambisonics domain have been proposed, as demonstrated in [Betlehem and Abhayapala \(2005\)](#) and [Lecomte et al. \(2018\)](#). However, significant challenges are still expected to remain at both low and high frequencies. Additionally, applying inverse filtering after conventional Ambisonics decoding introduces robustness issues. By capturing a separate direct sound field, this can be rendered using the VBAP method. In this way, the direction of arrival (DOA) can be preserved, while at the same time the sound field at high frequencies will more closely represent the true direct sound field, including the interaural cues. Although ideally this direct sound field component would be the only component arriving at the ears of the listener, the beamforming will not be perfect, and additional reverberant components will be included in the beamformed signal as well. In addition, the playback via VBAP in the playback room will cause additional reverberant components. The central assumption in our approach is that these unintended reverberant components, as they appear at the listener's ears in the playback environment, will be lower in level than the reverberant components heard in the recording environment. As a consequence, to perceptually match the sound field heard in the recording environment, additional reverberation needs to be reproduced in the playback environment, specifically to compensate for what is missing when reproducing the VBAP components. A loudspeaker array is employed in the reproduction room to reproduce the reverberant sound, in principle using Ambisonics, but adapted to compensate for spectral and spatial distortions of the sound field caused by the playback environment. To achieve a perceptual match between the fully reproduced reverberant sound field and the reverberation in the recording venue, three perceptual criteria will be optimized. First, the spectral shape of the fully reproduced reverberant sound field should match that of the recording venue. Second, the early decay curves of both the recording and reproduction rooms should be aligned. Third, to preserve spatial impression, the interaural cross correlation (IACC) should also match between the recording and reproduction. The selection of the three criteria considered in this study is motivated by their established links to perceptual attributes of reflections. The spectral distribution of the late reverberation field has been shown to influence timbral qualities, with an emphasis on low-frequency reverberation time contributing to perceived warmth and periodic structures in the reflection pattern leading to coloration ([Kuttruff, 2016](#)). The early decay curve (EDC) forms the basis for widely used parameters such as energy decay time (EDT) and T_{30} ,

which are standardized in [ISO \(2009\)](#) and provide reliable correlates of perceived reverberance. Finally, the IACC has been extensively validated as a predictor of spatial attributes: It correlates strongly with apparent source width (ASW) and listener envelopment (LEV) ([Ando, 1985](#); [Bradley and Souladre, 1995](#)). Together, these criteria capture the dominant perceptual dimensions affected by reflections, namely timbre, reverberance, and spatial impression. Two dummy heads are placed in both the recording and playback rooms for the optimization process to enable comparison of these perceptual criteria. Although these perceptual criteria may initially seem limited in describing the full sound field, research in parametric spatial audio coding has shown that such perceptual descriptions can effectively represent spatial audio with high quality ([Breebaart et al., 2005](#); [Breebaart et al., 2007](#)). To enable adjustment of the spectral properties of the direct and reverberant sound fields, as well as control over the energy decay curve of the combined sound field and the IACC, the spherical harmonic components are spectrally shaped using frequency-dependent weighting factors ($g_{dir}^{(i)}$, $g_{rev}^{(i)}$, and $\mathbf{M}_{wxyz\mathbf{R}}^{(i)}$) prior to rendering. These weighting factors are key parameters in the optimization process, which will be described in [Sec. IV](#). Before the optimization process can be described, a precise description of the signal path from capturing to rendering needs to be formulated. For this, in [Sec. III](#), the process of signal recording and reproduction is described. This section includes three subsections: direct and reverberant sound capturing ([Sec. III A](#)), direct sound filtering and rendering ([Sec. III B](#)), and finally, reverberant sound filtering and rendering ([Sec. III C](#)).

A. Direct and reverberant sound capturing

In the approach presented here, similar to DirAC ([Pulkki, 2007](#)), the direct and reverberant sounds are captured and processed separately. To capture the direct sound, an axisymmetric beamformer with the narrowest main beam ([Rafaely, 2015](#)), and with a DOA angle of $(\theta_{DOA}, \varphi_{DOA})$ is directed towards the sound source:

$$S_{BF}(k) = \sum_{n=0}^4 \sum_{m=-n}^n A_n^m(k) Y_n^m(\theta_{DOA}, \varphi_{DOA}). \quad (9)$$

Here, the “BF” subscript stands for “BeamFormer.” The elevation and azimuth of DOA $(\theta_{DOA}, \varphi_{DOA})$ can either be predetermined or estimated. In this paper, only the predetermined DOA information is used for beamforming.

To capture the reverb signal, the direct sound is subtracted from the full recorded sound field. To accomplish this, the beamformed signal with the corresponding DOA [Eq. (9)] is spatialized using the plane wave model from [Eq. \(2\)](#) and then subtracted from the encoded Ambisonics channels. The spatialized beamformed signal for order n and degree m is

$$S_{nBF}^m(k) = S_{BF}(k) [Y_n^m(\theta_{DOA}, \varphi_{DOA})], \quad (10)$$

and the reverberant field is obtained after subtraction from the recorded SH coefficients:

$$S_n^m \text{Rev}(k) = A_n^m(k) - S_n^m \text{BF}(k). \quad (11)$$

Here, “Rev” stand for “Reverberation.” In this computation, it is assumed, as mentioned earlier, that only one source is present.

B. Direct sound filtering and rendering

The upper signal flow in Fig. 1, shown in blue, corresponds to the rendering of the direct sound. Two options are available: Ambisonics or VBAP using a loudspeaker triplet. VBAP was selected for rendering the direct sound primarily for practical reasons. In our setup, the dense 50-loudspeaker layout would in principle support at least 5th-order Ambisonics decoding, and prior work has shown that when the Ambisonics order is chosen appropriately for the loudspeaker density and max- r_E weighting is applied, the resulting directional accuracy for sources panned inside a loudspeaker triangle can be perceptually very similar to VBAP (Zotter and Frank, 2019). In such situations, differences between the two rendering approaches are dominated by the loudspeaker geometry rather than the algorithm itself. Because implementing a high-order AllRAD (Zotter and Frank, 2012) and max- r_E weighting would introduce an additional processing stage that is not central to the present investigation, VBAP provides a straightforward and efficient rendering option for the direct path. The VBAP gains are represented in a gain vector, \mathbf{G}_{vbap} ,

$$\mathbf{G}_{vbap} = [g_1 \ g_2 \ g_3]^T, \quad (12)$$

where, g_l represents the VBAP gain of loudspeaker number l . In the time domain, the signals from three VBAP loudspeakers are filtered using 4th-order Gammatone filterbank (Hohmann, 2002) before playback. The filtering process uses frequency-dependent gains $g_{dir}^{(i)}$ in Gammatone filter number i . The impulse response of the Gammatone filter number i is denoted by $\gamma^{(i)}[n]$. The gain $g_{dir}^{(i)}$ of Gammatone filter is applied to achieve spectral energy equalization of the direct sound within filter number i . The inverse discrete Fourier transform (IDFT) of the recorded direct sounds $S_{BF}(k)$ from Eq. (9) is denoted as $s_{BF}[n] = IDFT\{S_{BF}(k)\}$. The final driving signals for the direct sound, using three VBAP loudspeakers in Gammatone band i , are represented in a driving vector as follows:

$$\mathbf{D}_{dir}^{(i)} = \mathbf{G}_{vbap} g_{dir}^{(i)} \gamma^{(i)}[n] * S_{BF}[n]. \quad (13)$$

Here, “*” is the convolution operator, and both the $\mathbf{D}_{dir}^{(i)}$ matrix and \mathbf{G}_{vbap} vector have three rows. The total signal of the direct sound for the three loudspeakers is obtained after synthesis of the gammatone band signals.

C. Reverberant sound filtering and rendering

After obtaining the direct sound driving signals for the loudspeakers, the driving signals for the reverberant sound are calculated. The reverberant signal $S_n^m \text{Rev}(k)$ can be reproduced

in a manner similar to conventional Ambisonics. Considering the summation form of Eq. (7), the driving signal of loudspeaker l for the reproduction of reverberant sound field is

$$D_{l,\text{Rev}}(k) = g_l \sum_{n=0}^4 \sum_{m=-n}^n S_n^m \text{Rev}(k) Y_n^m(\theta_l, \phi_l). \quad (14)$$

In this formula, g_l denotes the loudspeaker-dependent Lebedev-grid weights. There is other multiplying weighting [applied to loudspeaker driving signals in Eq. (14)] that controls the mainlobes and sidelobes of reproduced directional patterns, such as the weights max- r_E described in Zotter and Frank (2012). The max- r_E weighting maximizes the energy towards the panning direction. In this study, a different type of weighting is applied.

The recorded reverberant Ambisonics signal obtained from Eq. (11) is renamed for simplicity and placed in the matrix \mathbf{S}_{Rev} :

$$\mathbf{S}_{\text{Rev}} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{0\text{Rev}}^0(k) \\ S_{1\text{Rev}}^{-1}(k) \\ S_{1\text{Rev}}^0(k) \\ S_{1\text{Rev}}^1(k) \\ S_{m\text{Rev}}^n(k) \end{bmatrix} \equiv \begin{bmatrix} W_{\text{Rev}}(k) \\ Y_{\text{Rev}}(k) \\ X_{\text{Rev}}(k) \\ Z_{\text{Rev}}(k) \\ \mathbf{R}_{\text{Rev}}(k) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

In this context, $W_{\text{Rev}}(k)$ is related to the omni-directional 0th-order Ambisonics, while three channels of $Y_{\text{Rev}}(k)$, $X_{\text{Rev}}(k)$, and $Z_{\text{Rev}}(k)$ are related to the 1st-order Ambisonics or dipoles. In the Ambisonics context, these four channels are referred to as the B-format. The matrix $\mathbf{R}_{\text{Rev}}(k)$ has 21 rows, including all recorded Ambisonics channels for the remaining orders $2 \leq n \leq 4$. The Ambisonics coefficients of reverb sound are used to construct the driving signal of loudspeaker number l , where $1 \leq l \leq L$. According to Eq. (14), the driving signal for each harmonic can be separated. For example, the driving signals for the omni pattern $W_{\text{Rev}}(k)$ and the dipole component $Y_{\text{Rev}}(k)$ in Eq. (15) are

$$W_l(k) = g_l W_{\text{Rev}}(k) Y_0^0(\theta_l, \phi_l),$$

$$Y_l(k) = g_l Y_{\text{Rev}}(k) Y_1^{-1}(\theta_l, \phi_l). \quad (16)$$

In this way, all the driving signals of separated Ambisonic channels in the frequency domain can be arranged into another matrix, \mathbf{D}_l :

$$\mathbf{D}_l = \begin{bmatrix} W_l(k) \\ Y_l(k) \\ X_l(k) \\ Z_l(k) \\ \mathbf{R}_l(k) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

The \mathbf{D}_l matrix contains all Ambisonics driving signals for loudspeaker l . The time-domain equivalent of \mathbf{D}_l is $\mathbf{d}_l = IDFT\{\mathbf{D}_l\}$:

$$\mathbf{d}_l = \begin{bmatrix} w_l[n] \\ y_l[n] \\ x_l[n] \\ z_l[n] \\ \mathbf{r}_l[n] \end{bmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

Each row in Eq. (18) is filtered by a Gammatone filterbank. The filtered signal in band i is obtained as follows:

$$\mathbf{d}_l^{(i)} = (\gamma^{(i)}[n] \otimes \mathbf{1}_{25 \times 1}) \bar{*} \mathbf{d}_l = \begin{bmatrix} w_l^{(i)}[n] \\ y_l^{(i)}[n] \\ x_l^{(i)}[n] \\ z_l^{(i)}[n] \\ \mathbf{r}_l^{(i)}[n] \end{bmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

Here, \otimes represents the Kronecker product, and 25 is the number channels for 4th-order Ambisonics. The vector $\mathbf{1}_{25 \times 1}$ is a 25×1 vector where all elements are equal to 1. Therefore, $\gamma^{(i)}[n] \otimes \mathbf{1}_{25 \times 1}$ is a matrix with 25 rows, where each row is equal to the filter $\gamma^{(i)}[n]$. The operator ($\bar{*}$) is defined as a row-wise matrix convolution, meaning that each row of the first matrix is convolved with the corresponding row in the second matrix.

A mixing vector, $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$, is used to combine Ambisonics channels for the Gammatone band number i . In Sec. IV B, we will see how $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$ is utilized to control the IC at the position of the listener in the playback room. The mixing vector $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$ consists of the following elements:

$$\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)} = \begin{bmatrix} w^{(i)} \\ y^{(i)} \\ x^{(i)} \\ z^{(i)} \\ r^{(i)} \mathbf{1}_{21 \times 1} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

For the 0th Ambisonics $W^{(i)}$ and the three dipole 1st-order Ambisonics components $Y^{(i)}$, $X^{(i)}$, and $Z^{(i)}$, separate mixing coefficients $w^{(i)}$, $y^{(i)}$, $x^{(i)}$, and $z^{(i)}$ are used, respectively. For the HOA channels, denoted as $\mathbf{R}^{(i)}$, which correspond to orders of 2, 3, and 4, a single mixing coefficient, $r^{(i)}$, is used for simplification. To limit the computational load of the grid search optimization (described in Sec. IV B), only the 1st-order Ambisonics channels (B-format) were optimized individually, while a single coefficient, $r^{(i)}$, was applied to the remaining higher-order channels. This choice is justified by the lower effective energy and poorer signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of higher-order components at perceptually critical low and mid-frequencies, as well as by the limited usable frequency ranges of the Eigenmike (Table I). Specifically, below 1500 Hz, where the IC is most relevant,

the 2nd order contributes between 400 and 1500 Hz, the 3rd order between 1000 and 1500 Hz, and the 4th order does not contribute at all. After mixing the Ambisonics channels, a Gammatone weighting factor, $g_{rev}^{(i)}$, is applied. The driving signal of each loudspeaker for the reverb sound in Gammatone band i is given by

$$\mathbf{d}_{l,rev}^{(i)}[n] = g_{rev}^{(i)} \left(\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)} \right)^T \mathbf{d}_l^{(i)}, \quad 1 \leq l \leq L. \quad (21)$$

The mixing vectors $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$, combined with the reverb gains $g_{rev}^{(i)}$, control both IC and the energy of the reverb field in the reproduction room. Note that, unlike $g_l(k)$ in Eq. (14), frequency-dependent $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$ is not loudspeaker-dependent and is applied identically to all loudspeakers. Similar to the direct sound, the total signal of reverberant sound for the loudspeakers is obtained after synthesis of the gammatone band signals.

The gains of the Gammatone filters for direct ($g_{dir}^{(i)}$) and reverb ($g_{rev}^{(i)}$) sounds, and mixing coefficients of reverb channels ($\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$) are determined through an optimization procedure, as depicted in the optimization block in Fig. 1. In this process, the reproduced binaural room impulse response (BRIR) in the playback room will be adapted in the optimization and compared with that of the reference dummy head in the recording room. The mathematical details of the optimization are further explained in Sec. IV.

IV. OPTIMIZATION

For perceptually based room compensation, various types of information are crucial. In particular, for the perception of direct sound, the DOA is vital. This information is closely tied to spatial cues such as the interaural time difference (ITD) and interaural level difference (ILD) (Blauert, 1997), as well as the precedence effect (Litovsky *et al.*, 1999), which emphasizes the importance of the first wavefront reaching the ears. This is achieved by reproducing the sound source from the desired DOA and applying frequency-dependent direct gains $g_{dir}^{(i)}$. Beyond direct sound, the reverberant field provides essential cues related to envelopment, diffusion, brightness, and coloration, all influenced by natural reverberation. Additionally, the ratio between direct and reverberant sound conveys valuable information about the perceived spaciousness and distance of the sound source (Mershon and King, 1975). To manage the reverberant sound field and balance the direct and reverberant energy components, reverberant gains $g_{rev}^{(i)}$ are applied. Another relevant important parameter is the IC between the left and right ears, which influences the perception of directionality, distance, and the spatial qualities of sound (Blauert, 1997). In our approach, the IC is controlled using a mixing coefficient, denoted as $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$.

To determine $g_{dir}^{(i)}$, $g_{rev}^{(i)}$, and $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$, two dummy heads are used in the recording and reproduction rooms. For this optimization, the BRIRs of the source (as a reference), the room impulse responses (RIRs) of the microphones in the

recording room, and the BRIRs of the playback loudspeakers in the reproduction room are required. The dummy head in the recording room is positioned near the recording microphone to capture spatial cues accurately.

A. Direct sound optimization

For the optimization of direct sound, the BRIR in recording room is required along with the binaural Room-in-Room (RinR) impulse response of entire reproduction chain, denoted as $BRinR_{BF}$. The RIR of the recording microphone for the target source is beamformed, and the component $H_{BF}(k)$ and reverb component $H_{n\text{Rev}}^m(k)$ are obtained following a similar approach as in Eqs. (9) and (11). Here, instead of the recorded direct signal $S_{BF}(k)$ and the recorded reverb signal $S_{n\text{Rev}}^m(k)$, we work with the RIRs of the direct and the reverb parts. The BRIR vector for the VBAP loudspeakers in the reproduction room at the left ear is given by

$$\mathbf{BRIR}_{dir, left} = \begin{bmatrix} BRIR_{SP_1, left}[n] \\ BRIR_{SP_2, left}[n] \\ BRIR_{SP_3, left}[n] \end{bmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

For simplicity in notation, we omit the *left* subscript from this point forward. However, it is important to note that the \mathbf{BRIR}_{dir} and other BRIRs can still be considered for both the left and right ears. According to Eq. (13), the $BRinR_{BF}$ is obtained by convolving the BRIRs of three loudspeakers (SP_1, SP_2, SP_3) with the beamformed direct RIR in time domain $h_{BF}(n)$, while incorporating all processing steps:

$$BRinR_{BF}[n] = g_{dir}^{(i)} \gamma^{(i)}[n] * h_{BF}[n] * (\mathbf{G}_{vbap}^T \mathbf{BRIR}_{dir}). \quad (23)$$

The reference BRIR recorded in the recording room can be decomposed into its direct and reverberant components

$$BRIR_{ref}[n] = BRIR_{ref, dir}[n] + BRIR_{ref, rev}[n]. \quad (24)$$

The $BRinR_{BF}$ in Eq. (23) can also be decomposed into its direct and reverb components:

$$BRinR_{BF}[n] = BRinR_{BF, dir}[n] + BRinR_{BF, rev}[n]. \quad (25)$$

It was shown in Grosse and van de Par (2015) that the separation times between $BRIR_{ref, dir}[n]$ and $BRIR_{ref, rev}[n]$, as well as the separation time between $BRinR_{BF, dir}[n]$ and $BRinR_{BF, rev}[n]$, play an important role in determining the reverberation time (T_{30}). In this study, these parameters have been set empirically rather than optimized. Instead of attempting to make $BRIR_{ref, dir}$ and $BRinR_{BF, dir}[n]$ identical, as is done in conventional inverse filtering, we compensate for their respective spectral energies. This approach ensures a more robust perceptually driven filtering process. It is implemented using a Gammatone analysis and synthesis framework (Hohmann, 2002), which enables adjustment to the auditory transfer function (ATF) of the measured reference and reproduced BRIRs. The $ATF_{sig}^{(i)}$ is defined as the

energy of a signal at the output of filter number i of the Gammatone filterbank. The goal of direct sound filtering is to equalize the spectral energies of the beamformed direct signal, reproduced by VBAP in the reproduction room [Eq. (24)], with the spectral energy of direct part of reference signal $BRIR_{ref, dir}$ [Eq. (25)]:

$$\begin{aligned} ATF^{(i)}(BRIR_{ref, dir, left}[n]) \\ = \left(g_{dir, left}^{(i)}\right)^2 ATF^{(i)}(BRinR_{BF, left}[n]). \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

We added the subscript “*left*” to indicate that different gain values can be obtained for the left and right ears. For gain optimization, we employ a fast-converging method proposed in van de Par *et al.* (2005), which ensures that negative gains are avoided for overlapping Gammatone filters. This optimization approach was also used in Grosse and van de Par (2015). A weighted average of the gains obtained for the left and right ears can be applied for the loudspeakers, ensuring balanced and perceptually accurate reproduction:

$$g_{dir}^{(i)} = x g_{dir, left}^{(i)} + (1 - x) g_{dir, right}^{(i)}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1. \quad (27)$$

The x value can be set to 0.5 for normal averaging. The reconstructed direct sound after direct-sound optimization using $g_{dir}^{(i)}$ for Gammatone Filterbank synthesis is

$$\begin{aligned} BRinR_{BF, opt}[n] \\ = \text{GammatoneSynthesis}_{i=1:N_G} \left\{ g_{dir}^{(i)} BRinR_{BF}^{(i)}[n] \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Here, N_G represents the number of Gammatone filters and the $BRinR_{BF, opt}[n]$ denotes the optimized direct signals. However, similar to Eq. (25), the $BRinR_{BF, opt}[n]$ can once again be decomposed into its direct and reverb components:

$$BRinR_{BF, opt}[n] = BRinR_{BF, opt, dir}[n] + BRinR_{BF, opt, rev}[n]. \quad (29)$$

Here, the $BRinR_{BF, opt, dir}[n]$ represents the optimized direct sound, while the $BRinR_{BF, opt, rev}[n]$ refers to an unavoidable component of the direct sound caused by the reverberation of the playback room. This component is taken into account when optimization the reverb sound in Sec. IV B.

B. Reverb sound optimization

A parameter required for optimization is the reproduced binaural RinR impulse response of the reverberant room, denoted as $BRinR_{Rev}$. This impulse response is obtained by convolving the recorded reverberant RIRs with the BRIRs of all loudspeakers in the reproduction room, taking into account the entire processing chain. To obtain the reverberant RIR in the SH domain, the spatialized direct signal is subtracted from the original recorded RIR in the SH domain, similarly to Eq. (11). A notation similar to that used in Eqs. (15)–(21) can be applied, substituting the signals with the BRIRs and RIRs. Following the approach presented in

Eq. (15), a recorded reverberant RIR in the Ambisonics domain can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{H}_{\text{Rev}} = \begin{bmatrix} H_{0\text{Rev}}^0(k) \\ H_{1\text{Rev}}^{-1}(k) \\ H_{1\text{Rev}}^0(k) \\ H_{1\text{Rev}}^1(k) \\ \mathbf{H}_{m\text{Rev}}^n(k) \end{bmatrix} \equiv \begin{bmatrix} W_h(k) \\ Y_h(k) \\ X_h(k) \\ Z_h(k) \\ \mathbf{R}_h(k) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (30)$$

Here, the subscript “ h ” indicates that the Ambisonic signals correspond to impulse responses. Similar to Eqs. (18) and (19), the driving signal for loudspeaker number l , this time for the recorded reverberant RIRs, can be expressed at the output of the Gammatone filter number i as

$$\mathbf{d}_{h,l}^{(i)} = \begin{bmatrix} w_{h,l}^{(i)}[n] \\ y_{h,l}^{(i)}[n] \\ x_{h,l}^{(i)}[n] \\ z_{h,l}^{(i)}[n] \\ \mathbf{r}_{h,l}^{(i)}[n] \end{bmatrix}. \quad (31)$$

By considering Eq. (21) together with the BRIRs of loudspeaker array ($BRIR_l, 1 \leq l \leq L$), $BRinR_{\text{Rev}}$ can be obtained as follows:

$$BRinR_{\text{Rev}}^{(i)}[n] = g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)} \left(\mathbf{M}_{\text{wyzR}}^{(i)} \right)^T \times \left(\sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{d}_{h,l}^{(i)} \bar{*} (BRIR_l \otimes \mathbf{1}_{25 \times 1}) \right). \quad (32)$$

Here, the driving signals of loudspeaker number l comprising all Ambisonics channels filtered by the i th Gammatone filter, denoted as $\mathbf{d}_{h,l}^{(i)}$, are convolved with the respected $BRIR_l$. After summing across all loudspeakers in the array, those signals are weighted using loudspeaker-independent mixing coefficients ($\mathbf{M}_{\text{wyzR}}^{(i)}$). Subsequently, the energy-compensating gain $g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)}$ is applied for each channel. It should again be noted that both $BRIR_l$ and $BRinR_{\text{Rev}}^{(i)}[n]$ can be considered for either the left or right ear. For optimizing the reverberant RIR, the IC between the left and right ears is taken into account. The main idea to compensate the IC in the center of the loudspeaker array involves using only two Ambisonics channels: the W and Y channels (Fallah and van de Par, 2020). The W channel, representing the 0th-order Ambisonics, exhibits an omnidirectional pattern, while the Y channel, representing one of the 1st-order components, features a dipole pattern aligned with the line connecting the left and right ears of the dummy head in both the recording room and the center of the reproduction array. The W channel is intended to produce an in-phase signal, whereas the Y channel generates an out-of-phase signal between the ears. Consequently, a weighted combination of

these two channels is expected to establish the desired IC. By using only the W and Y channels, the $BRinR_{\text{Rev}}$ in Eq. (32) can be modified to

$$BRinR_{\text{Rev,WY}}^{(i)}[n] = g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)} \left(\mathbf{M}_{\text{wy}}^{(i)} \right)^T \times \left(\sum_{l=1}^L \begin{bmatrix} w_{h,l}^{(i)}[n] \\ y_{h,l}^{(i)}[n] \end{bmatrix} \bar{*} \left(BRIR_l \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right) \right). \quad (33)$$

In this approach, it is also possible to select specific combinations of Ambisonics channels, for example, $BRinR_{\text{Rev,WY}}$, $BRinR_{\text{Rev,WYX}}$, $BRinR_{\text{Rev,WYZ}}$, or $BRinR_{\text{Rev,XYZ}}$, instead of utilizing all Ambisonic channels in $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wyzR}}^{(i)}$. Here, the W and Y channels are always retained due to their essential role in controlling IC. For these types of truncated Ambisonic representations, the corresponding mixing vectors are denoted as $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wy}}^{(i)}$, $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wyzx}}^{(i)}$, $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wyz}}^{(i)}$, and $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wyzx}}^{(i)}$, respectively. However, in the general case, all Ambisonics channels, as indicated in Eq. (32), are utilized for the reproduction of the reverberant field. Nonetheless, the impact of using a truncated set of Ambisonics channels can be investigated. In our approach, adding the X channel to the basic WY configuration is expected to enhance robustness during reproduction, particularly when listeners change their head position or orientation. Another important consideration is the complexity of optimization and computational load. To reduce this complexity, separate mixing weights are applied only to the 0th- and 1st-order Ambisonics channels (W, Y, X, and Z), while a constant weight is assigned to the remaining higher-order channels, as defined in Eq. (20). In the general case where all Ambisonic channels are used, as described in Eq. (32), the total reproduced reverberant BRIR in the playback room is obtained by summing the reverberant components from Eqs. (29) and (32):

$$BRinR_{\text{Total Rev}}^{(i)}[n] = BRinR_{\text{BF,opt,rev}}^{(i)}[n] + g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)} \left(\mathbf{M}_{\text{wyzR}}^{(i)} \right)^T \times \left(\sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{d}_{h,l}^{(i)} \bar{*} (BRIR_l \otimes \mathbf{1}_{25 \times 1}) \right). \quad (34)$$

In Eq. (34), the signal $BRinR_{\text{BF,opt,rev}}^{(i)}[n]$ is included because the VBAP loudspeakers used for reproducing the direct sound generate a non-separable reverberant component. The combination of Ambisonics mixing coefficients $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wyzR}}^{(i)}$ and the gain factors $g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)}$ enables control over the reproduced IC and the overall reverberant energy, respectively. In cases where the T_{30} of the reproduction room is shorter than that of the recording room, the $BRinR_{\text{BF,opt,rev}}^{(i)}[n]$ in Eq. (29) contains less reverberation energy than required, potentially resulting in an under-represented or less immersive reverberant field. Therefore, additional reverberation can be added according to Eq. (34). A general observation about this approach is that it only supports scenarios where the

reproduction room has a T_{30} that is equal to or shorter than that of the recording room. Fortunately, this condition typically holds true in practice. Recordings are often made during concert events held in large halls, while reproduction usually takes place in smaller rooms. To determine the optimal values of the $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$ vector for controlling IC between left and right ear signals, a grid search algorithm is employed. This algorithm explores various combinations of parameters $w^{(i)}$, $y^{(i)}$, $x^{(i)}$, $z^{(i)}$, and $\mathbf{r}^{(i)}$, using predefined value ranges with a constant step size for each:

$$-[\alpha \beta \chi \delta \varepsilon]^T \leq [w^{(i)} y^{(i)} x^{(i)} z^{(i)} r^{(i)}]^T \leq [\alpha \beta \chi \delta \varepsilon]^T. \quad (35)$$

In this way, for each combination of $[\alpha \beta \chi \delta \varepsilon]$, similar to the direct sound energy optimization described in Eq. (26), an optimal gain of $g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)}$ can be determined. This gain ensures that the ATF of the reproduced reverb field matches that of the reverberant reference:

$$\begin{aligned} ATF^{(i)}(BRIR_{\text{ref,rev,left}}[n]) \\ = ATF^{(i)}(BRinR_{\text{BF,opt,rev,left}}^{(i)}[n]) + (g_{\text{rev,left}}^{(i)})^2 \\ \times ATF^{(i)}\left(\left(\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}\right)^T \left(\sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{d}_{h,l}^{(i)*}(BRIR_l \otimes \mathbf{1}_{25 \times 1})\right)\right). \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

Here, following the assumption in Grosse and van de Par (2015), the two reverberant components, $BRinR_{\text{BF,opt,rev}}^{(i)}[n]$ and $BRinR_{\text{Rev}}^{(i)}[n]$, are considered uncorrelated. Similar to the gain averaging approach used for VBAP loudspeakers in Eq. (27), a weighted average of the left and right ear gains can be used as the final gain for the loudspeaker array in each frequency band:

$$g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)} = y g_{\text{rev,left}}^{(i)} + (1 - y) g_{\text{rev,right}}^{(i)}, \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1. \quad (37)$$

This allows for balanced energy adjustment across both ears. For playback of the compensated reverberant sound, all loudspeakers in the array are utilized. Both the $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$ and $g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)}$ are applied to filter the reverberant Ambisonics signal of each loudspeaker prior to playback. The total reproduced BRIR in each frequency band is obtained by summing the optimized direct component from Eq. (29) and the reverberant component, which is processed using a predefined matrix, $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$, and its corresponding optimized $g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)}$ from Eq. (32), as follows:

$$BRinR^{(i)}[n] = BRinR_{\text{BF,opt}}[n] + BRinR_{\text{Rev}}^{(i)}[n]. \quad (38)$$

For this signal, the IACC and IC for Gammatone band number (i) are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} IACC_{BRinR^{(i)}}[q] &= \frac{\sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} BRinR_{\text{left}}^{(i)}[m] BRinR_{\text{right}}^{(i)}[m+q]}{\sqrt{\sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} (BRinR_{\text{left}}^{(i)}[m])^2} \sqrt{\sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} (BRinR_{\text{right}}^{(i)}[m])^2}} \\ IC_{BRinR^{(i)}} &= \max(IACC_{BRinR^{(i)}}). \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

The IC between $BRinR_{\text{left}}^{(i)}$ and $BRinR_{\text{right}}^{(i)}$, denoted as $IC_{BRinR^{(i)}}$, is computed and compared with the reference IC, $IC_{\text{ref}^{(i)}}$. The reference IC is calculated between the signals $BRIR_{\text{ref,left}}^{(i)}[n]$ and $BRIR_{\text{ref,right}}^{(i)}[n]$, as defined in Eq. (24). For each combination of mixing coefficients $[\alpha \beta \chi \delta \varepsilon]^T$ and its corresponding gain $g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)}$, an absolute error function is calculated. The combination that minimizes the IC error is selected as the final reverb-compensating mixing coefficients and gain for each frequency band:

$$\min_{\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}:g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)}} \{IC_{\text{error}^{(i)}}\} = \min_{\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}:g_{\text{rev}}^{(i)}} \left\{ |IC_{BRinR_{\text{opt}}^{(i)}} - IC_{\text{ref}^{(i)}}| \right\}. \quad (40)$$

The optimization ensures that the reproduced reverberant signal closely matches the spatial characteristics of the reference in terms of IC. The optimization procedure for

both direct and reverb components is summarized in Algorithm 1.

As mentioned earlier, it is possible to use only 1st-order Ambisonics (B-format) and even truncated versions of 1st-order Ambisonics, instead of the full $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$. To investigate the impact of using different numbers of Ambisonics channels, several configurations are considered in the optimization process, including the full B-format $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wxyzR}}^{(i)}$ and the truncated versions $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wy}}^{(i)}$, $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wyz}}^{(i)}$, and $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wyz}}^{(i)}$. For instance, in the case of $\mathbf{M}_{\text{wy}}^{(i)}$, only the coefficients $w^{(i)}$ and $y^{(i)}$ are optimized.

For this case, the grid search algorithm is then limited to searching within the defined ranges, $-\alpha \leq w^{(i)} \leq \alpha$ and $-\beta \leq y^{(i)} \leq \beta$. This approach allows for analysis of how reducing the number of Ambisonics channels affects the accuracy of spatial reproduction and IC control.

ALGORITHM 1. Calculation of the optimal parameters $g_{dir}^{(i)}$, $\mathbf{M}_{\text{WXYZR}}^{(i)}$, and $g_{rev}^{(i)}$.

-
- Step 1.** Determination of direct sound energy-compensating gains $g_{dir}^{(i)}$ using Eqs. (26) and (27).
- Step 2.** Determination of optimal reverb mixing coefficients $\mathbf{M}_{\text{WXYZR}}^{(i)}$ and energy-compensating gains $g_{rev}^{(i)}$:
- (1) Setting the elements of $\mathbf{M}_{\text{WXYZR}}^{(i)}$, $[w^{(i)} y^{(i)} x^{(i)} z^{(i)} r^{(i)}]^T$, to predefined values according to Eq. (35).
 - (2) An optimal $g_{rev}^{(i)}$ is determined for the set of $[w^{(i)} y^{(i)} x^{(i)} z^{(i)} r^{(i)}]^T$ in sub-step (1) according to the Eqs. (36) and (37).
 - (3) Calculation of the total reproduced RIR $BRinR^{(i)}[n]$ in Eq. (38).
 - (4) The reproduced IC between left and right ears for $BRinR^{(i)}[n]$ is calculated according to Eq. (39).
 - (5) The error functions for ICs of reference and reproduced BRIRs are calculated: $IC_{error^{(i)}} = |IC_{BRinR^{(i)}} - IC_{ref^{(i)}}|$.
- Step 3.** A grid searching for $-\alpha \leq w^{(i)} \leq \alpha$, $-\beta \leq y^{(i)} \leq \beta$, $-\chi \leq x^{(i)} \leq \chi$, $-\delta \leq z^{(i)} \leq \delta$, and $-\alpha \leq r^{(i)} \leq \alpha$ with the defined step size and repeating the sub-steps (1), (2), (3), (4) and (5) in **Step 2** to find $\mathbf{M}_{\text{WXYZR}}^{(i)}$ and its corresponding $g_{rev}^{(i)}$ that give the minimum error in Eq. (40).
-

V. EVALUATION OF THE METHOD

A. Measurements

Two sets of recordings in different rooms were conducted to evaluate the proposed method. The first set was recorded at the Theater Laboratorium and the second at St. Christophorus Church, both located in Oldenburg, Germany, as depicted in Fig. 2. The T_{30} value in the theater is approximately 500 ms, whereas in the church it is around 1500 ms. Measurements were conducted to compare acoustic characteristics under different reverberation conditions. The mh acoustics EM32 Eigenmike (mh acoustics, 2023) and the KEMAR dummy head (GRAS, 2025) were employed as recording microphones, while Dynaudia Core 5 loudspeakers (Dynaudio, Skanderborg, Denmark) were used to play the excitation

sweeps for measuring RIRs and BRIRs. The Eigenmike was employed to capture both RIRs and recordings of music and speech. Two microphone positions were selected in each recording room. In the first position (Pos. 1), the microphone was placed nearly at an azimuth angle of 0° relative to the source, at an approximate distance of 10 m. In the second position (Pos.2), the source was located to the left of the microphone at an approximate distance of 15 m and an azimuthal angle of about 30° . The positions of the KEMAR dummy head and the Eigenmike were arranged to minimize mutual acoustic interference from reflections. To achieve this, the recording devices were placed at slightly different heights. In both positions in the theater and in Pos. 1 of the church, the Eigenmike was placed slightly lower and in front of the KEMAR dummy head. However, in the church, at Pos. 2, the dummy head was placed on a bench; therefore, the Eigenmike was positioned behind the dummy head and slightly higher. In addition to the RIR and BRIR measurements, live recordings of voice, piano, and violin performances were conducted in the Theater Laboratorium, along with a voice recording in the church. All recordings were made using an RME Fireface UFX+ audio interface (RME Audio, Haimhausen, Germany) at a sampling frequency of 44.1 kHz.

For audio reproduction, a loudspeaker array based on a 50-node Lebedev grid (Lecomte et al., 2016) was used, enabling the encoding and playback of 5th-order Ambisonics signals through real loudspeakers. This setup is located in the loudspeaker laboratory of the Acoustics Research Group at the University of Oldenburg, as depicted in Fig. 3. The array employs compact Genelec 8010 loudspeakers (Genelec, Iisalmi, Finland) and has a radius of approximately 1.5 m. The average T_{30} measured at the center of the array in this reproduction environment is approximately 500 ms.

FIG. 2. Measurement setups were deployed in two acoustically different rooms in Oldenburg. (Right) Theater Laboratorium ($T_{30} \approx 500$ ms). (Left) St. Christophorus Church ($T_{30} \approx 1500$ ms). In both rooms, a KEMAR dummy head microphone and an Eigenmike were used to capture BRIRs and spatial RIRs, respectively.

FIG. 3. Loudspeaker array setup in the loudspeaker laboratory of the Acoustics Group in Oldenburg, featuring 50 loudspeakers arranged according to a 50-node Lebedev grid. The array has a radius of approximately 1.5 m and is located in an environment with an average T_{30} of about 500 ms at the central listening position. This setup was used for the spatial reproduction of 5th-order Ambisonics signals.

B. Optimization results

For the optimization, we used the recorded BRIRs captured with the KEMAR dummy head and the RIRs captured with the Eigenmike in the recording rooms, together with

the BRIRs of 50 loudspeakers measured with KEMAR in the reproduction room. At a sampling frequency of 44.1 kHz, 42 Gammatone filters were employed for analysis and synthesis in the proposed approach.

The optimization results for the processed RIRs, compared to the reference BRIRs in the theater at Pos. 2 are shown in Fig. 4. In the optimization process, as defined in Eq. (24), the first 10 ms of the reference BRIRs were considered the direct part, while the remainder was treated as the reverberant part. The theater environment, with a T_{30} of approximately 500 ms that is comparable to that of the playback room, presents a challenging scenario for preserving spatial and spectral characteristics during reproduction. The two upper panels in Fig. 4 display the ATFs of the reproduced BRIRs for the left and right ears. These panels compare the ATFs of four processed versions (using WY, WYX, WYXZ, and WYXZR) with those of the reference (Ref) and the unprocessed conventional Ambisonics case (UnP). It is important to note that in the UnP case, the recorded Ambisonics signal is decoded using Eq. (7) and then reproduced without any further processing.

As expected, due to the larger amount of reverberation, the ATFs of the conventional Ambisonics case (UnP) exhibit noticeable deviations from the reference, particularly

FIG. 4. Comparison of four processed rendering cases (WY, WYX, WYXZ, and WYXZR) with the reference (Ref) and the unprocessed conventional Ambisonics case (UnP) in the theater. The two upper panels show the acoustic transfer functions (ATFs) for the left and right ears across the reference, UnP, and processed cases. The processed methods exhibit improved spectral energy alignment with the reference across most Gammatone frequency bins. The lower left panel illustrates the ICs of the processed and UnP cases compared to the reference for perceptually relevant frequencies below 1500 Hz. Improvements are observed across most frequency bands in all processed cases, except for bins 5–11, where only the WYXZR case shows a strong match. The lower right panel presents Schroeder energy decay curves (EDCs) of the BRIRs, demonstrating enhanced decay characteristics and reverberation time alignment in the processed cases relative to the UnP case.

at low frequencies, where reverberant energy is more dominant. In contrast, the ATFs of the processed versions more closely align with those of the reference across most Gammatone frequency bands. However, in some low-frequency bands, where reverberation strongly dominates (e.g., bands 3 and 4), perfect compensation is not fully achieved. The lower left panel of Fig. 4 compares the IC values of the processed and UnP BRIRs with those of the reference signal across frequency bands up to band 19, corresponding to frequencies below 1500 Hz. This range is perceptually critical, as the auditory system is particularly sensitive to changes in IC at these frequencies. For Gammatone bands between 5 and 11, notable differences are observed among the compensation methods. The WYXZR case demonstrates the best alignment with the reference in this range, whereas the WY and WYXZ (B-format) cases show little to no improvement. There is a fundamental limitation due to the way the reproduced Ambisonics signals interact with the playback room acoustics. With the optimization proposed, there is no mathematical guarantee that the precise intended IC pattern can be fully restored. In practice, however, adjusting the strength of individual harmonics helps to compensate to a good degree, but the achievable match will not be perfect. Most Gammatone filterbank outputs for the compensated cases show improved IC, outperforming the UnP case, which lacks room compensation.

The lower right panel of Fig. 4 presents the Schroeder energy decay curves (EDCs) (Schroeder, 1965) for the reference, unprocessed, and processed cases. These curves show that the proposed method leads to improved T_{30} values. The observed difference in reverberation time exceeds 25 ms for a reference T_{30} of 0.5 s, corresponding to a relative change greater than 5%, which is above the just-noticeable difference (JND) threshold (Seraphim, 1958; ISO, 2009). Among the processed cases, the EDCs for WYXZ and WYXZR more closely align with the reference compared to those of WYX and WY. This improvement is primarily attributed to the limited low- and mid-frequency content in the HOA channels captured by the Eigenmike recordings (mh acoustics, 2023). Consequently, the WYXZ and WYXZR cases contribute less low-frequency reverberant energy during the optimization process, resulting in a shorter reverberation tail that better matches the reference.

The results for the church environment at Pos. 2 are shown in Fig. 5. The church exhibits a significantly higher T_{30} (~1500 ms) compared to the playback room (~500 ms), which facilitates the preservation of spatial and spectral characteristics during reproduction. According to the upper panels of Fig. 5 and similar to the results obtained for the theater, the ATFs of the processed cases achieve a much closer match to the reference across a wide range of Gammatone frequency bins. For IC, with the exception of a few Gammatone filters in certain cases, the processed

FIG. 5. Similar to Fig. 4, but showing results for the church environment. The compensated cases exhibit improved energy alignment across most Gammatone frequency bins. The processed cases also demonstrate significantly better IC alignment with the reference (Ref) compared to the conventional Ambisonics approach, except for a few frequency bins in some cases. For the EDCs, all processed cases closely replicate the reverberation characteristics of the reference, with shorter and more accurate decay profiles compared to the UnP case. These results highlight the effectiveness of the proposed method in typical scenarios where the T_{30} of the recording room is longer than that of the playback room.

signals show significant improvement over the UnP case, demonstrating better alignment with the reference. These improvements in IC indicate a closer match to the characteristic structure of the reference sound field. While deviations of direct-sound IC from natural reference conditions are known to affect spatial impression and the reliability of localization cues (Blauert, 1997; Fallor and Merimaa, 2004), IC should not be interpreted as a global predictor of localization accuracy in reverberant environments. In our optimization of the IC, the direct sound field is fixed, and optimizations are only applied to the SH representing the reverberant sound field. In this way the global IC can serve as a good metric to optimize the spatial diffuseness of the reverberant sound field.

For the EDCs, the highly reverberant nature of the church environment compared to the playback room provides greater flexibility for the proposed compensation method. The processed cases exhibit a closer alignment with the reference decay curve, indicating effective reverberation compensation. The improved matching observed in the WYXZR case is partly attributed to the reduced contribution of low-frequency reverberation in the HOA channels, as captured by the Eigenmike. This reduction leads to less added reverberation in these channels, resulting in a shorter and more accurate reverberation tail that more closely resembles the original acoustic environment.

The main difference between the theater and the church arises from their reverberation times. When the recording room has a longer T_{30} than the playback room, as in the case of the church, the direct sound reproduced in the playback room generates less reverberation than in the recording. This leaves perceptual space for the recorded reverberant component to be added, allowing the overall decay to reflect that of the original room. This condition allows greater flexibility in the compensation process across the entire frequency range. In contrast, when the recording and playback rooms have similar T_{30} values, as in the theater, our approach remains largely effective by compensating for frequency regions where coloration has been altered by the playback room. Overall, the results from both environments confirm the effectiveness of the proposed method in reproducing the spectral and spatial characteristics of the recordings, even when the recording and playback rooms exhibit similar reverberation times.

C. Perceptual evaluation

For the perceptual evaluation of the proposed method, a multi-stimulus listening test based on the multiple stimuli with hidden reference and anchor (MUSHRA) framework (ITU, 2003) was conducted for two headphone experiments and three loudspeaker rendering experiments. The purpose was to find how closely the proposed method matches the sound field recorded at the recording sites and how the proposed method compares to the conventional Ambisonics. Fourteen participants (6 male, 8 female) with normal

hearing, aged between 21 and 35 years (mean age 26 years), took part in both the headphone and loudspeaker experiments. The conditions presented to participants included the following: (i) a reference signal recorded with a dummy head in the recording room (Ref), (ii) a low-pass filtered version of the reference used as an anchor (Anchor), (iii) a signal reproduced in a reverberant room using conventional 4th-order Ambisonics with 25 channels and no room compensation (ConAmb), (iv) a 4th-order simulated anechoic Ambisonics reproduction using 50 loudspeakers (anechoic), (v) an optimized direct sound only rendered using VBAP, and (vi) five versions of the compensated signal generated using the proposed method, labeled WY, WYX, WYXZ, WYXZR, and WYZ. Note that the anechoic condition was included only in the first headphone-based experiment. For the anechoic condition, although additional equalization could theoretically improve the EM32 signals after radial filtering, Zotter *et al.* (2015) show that such processing depends strongly on the reproduction mode. Because low-frequency spatial characteristics differ fundamentally between free-field loudspeaker radiation and head-related transfer functions (HRTFs), a single equalization that performs consistently for both playback conditions is not feasible. Therefore, such equalization was not included in this study, which focuses on compensating the influence of the reproduction room. VBAP is used for rendering the direct sound. However, since the reproduction takes place in a reverberant playback room, this direct sound will naturally generate additional reverberation according to the T_{30} of room. In total, ten conditions were evaluated in the first headphone experiment, and nine conditions were evaluated in both the second headphone experiment and the loudspeaker experiment. Listeners were instructed to assign higher scores to audio samples that more closely resembled the reference signal, either in terms of overall similarity or in terms of a similarity to a specific evaluation criterion. In the headphone experiments, only the general similarity to the reference was assessed, whereas in the loudspeaker experiment, overall quality, timbral naturalness, and spatial naturalness were evaluated, all in terms of similarity to the presented reference. The test stimuli were generated by convolving five dry audio signals, namely snare drum, guitar, clarinet, and a male voice, with the corresponding BRIRs. Additionally, real recordings were captured using the Eigenmike array: a male voice, a piano piece, and a violin piece in the theater, and a male voice in the church. For both the theater and church conditions, only Pos. 2 was used for the convolved stimuli. For the real recordings in the theater, the piano performance corresponds approximately to Pos. 2, while the voice and violin recordings were captured near Pos. 1. In the church, the real recording (male voice) was captured at Pos. 1.

1. Headphone evaluations

This experiment was conducted with 14 listeners using headphones in a listening booth. Audio signals were presented at 70 dB sound pressure level (SPL) through Sennheiser HD 650 headphones (Sennheiser, Wedemark,

Germany), driven by an RME UFX+ soundcard, and equalized using AKtools (Brinkmann and Weinzierl, 2017) to ensure an almost flat frequency response. The headphone evaluation consisted of two parts. In the first part, the final rendering was simulated using recorded BRIRs from 50 loudspeakers, similar to those used in the optimization process. This setup allows for evaluating the method's effectiveness when the rendering and optimization are performed at the same positions for the convolved stimuli. However, for real voice, violin, and piano recordings captured in the theater, as well as voice recordings from the church, mismatches still exist between the recording and optimization positions. For these real recordings, the evaluation offers insight into the method's robustness with respect to variations on the recording side. For the first part of the headphone experiment, the mean scores and standard errors are shown in Fig. 6. The upper two panels illustrate the variability across subjects for each instrument recorded in the theater (upper left) and the church (upper right). In both panels, the hidden references (Ref) are not always correctly identified by the listeners, indicating that some test conditions produced signals of similar perceptual quality to the reference.

In both environments, the anchor signals were almost always identified, reflecting their consistently low perceived quality. In the upper left panel (theater recordings), the average scores for all instruments using ConAmb are lower than those of the compensated cases: WY, WYX, WYXZ, WYXZR, and WYZ. A similar trend is observed for the anechoic case. This suggests that 4th-order Ambisonics recording and reproduction alone are insufficient, and compensation is necessary even when the reproduction room does not include reflections. It was also shown that recordings with spherical microphones such as Eigenmike recordings can exhibit noticeably lower perceptual quality compared to reference recordings, highlighting the inherent limitations of the encoding process (Pfanzagl-Cardone, 2023). Further limitation is related to the reproduction side and the very small sweet spot for frequencies above 2.6 kHz in 4th-order Ambisonics reproduction, which is even smaller than the average human head size. Although the physical sweet area of low-order Ambisonics becomes narrower at high frequencies, the perceptual sweet spot may remain larger because listeners rely predominantly on low-frequency ITDs and mid-frequency ILDs for horizontal localization. While high-frequency components contribute to ILDs and timbral coloration, their spatial precision is perceptually less critical, so inaccuracies above approximately 2.6 kHz have reduced impact on directional perception compared to what the physical HOA limitations would suggest (Stitt *et al.*, 2014).

Interestingly, in the theater, a relatively dry environment with a high direct-to-reverberant ratio (DDR), the mean scores for the anechoic condition are consistently lower than those of the compensated direct sound (VBAP) for all instruments except the real violin. This highlights the importance of applying compensation, even when it is

applied only to the direct sound. Under the church condition, shown in the upper left panel, a similar trend is observed for all audio signals except for the real speech. The SNR for the real speech recording is low due to the distant placement of the talker from the Eigenmike and the presence of background noise. Additionally, the microphone capsules of the Eigenmike generate a certain amount of self-noise, which becomes more noticeable when the recorded signal level is low. This issue is less critical during the recording of RIRs, not only because the loudspeaker levels can be set higher, but also because the exponential sweep method increases the effective SNR by averaging out noise over the sweep duration (Farina, 2000). It is important to mention that compensating noisy Eigenmike recordings can result in colored noise, which tends to be more annoying than the original recorded noise. To reduce this effect for the speech recordings made in the church, the average noise profile across all stimuli was added to each stimulus, including the reference. Despite this compensation, for the real speech recording in the church, only the WYX and WYXZ cases exhibit higher mean scores compared to the VBAP and ConAmb cases. In contrast to the theater, in the church, only the clarinet receives higher scores with VBAP than with the anechoic condition; in all other cases, the anechoic case is rated higher. This can be explained by the fact that the church is a more reverberant space, where accurate rendering of the reverberant signal becomes more critical to perceived audio quality.

In the two lower panels of Fig. 6, the averaged results are shown for subject variation (lower left: results averaged first over instruments, followed by mean and standard deviation across subjects) and instrument variation (lower right: results averaged first over subjects, followed by mean and standard deviation across instruments). In both rooms, the use of ConAmb results in significant signal degradation, with average scores around 40% on a 100% scale. The anechoic case achieves slightly higher scores, ranging between 40% and 60%. This level of degradation suggests that even the anechoic Ambisonics reproduction fails to deliver perceptual quality comparable to that of a dummy head recording. The compensated direct sound (VBAP) provides only directional cues and does not fully reproduce all the desired characteristics of the reference signal. Its scores range between 40% and 60%, yet still remain higher than those of ConAmb. In the theater, a dry room with low reverberation, VBAP scores are higher than those of the anechoic condition. In contrast, in the church, where reverberation is stronger, VBAP scores fall below those of the anechoic case. In the compensated WY case, which utilizes only two Ambisonics channels, the required transmission data are significantly reduced compared to conventional HOA. Nevertheless, the mean scores for the WY case consistently exceed those of ConAmb, ranging between 60% and 70% in both environments. The results indicate that incorporating additional Ambisonics channels during reproduction can enhance audio quality. Notably, even the inclusion of just one extra channel, as seen in the WYX and WYZ cases,

FIG. 6. General quality assessment results from the first part of the headphone experiment. The mean scores and standard errors across subjects are shown for various audio signals in the theater (upper left) and church (upper right). The lower panels display the overall mean and standard errors across all subjects and instruments. The lower left panel shows variation across subjects, while the lower right panel illustrates variation across instruments. The participants' ratings indicate that conventional Ambisonics (ConAmb) and simulated anechoic Ambisonics reproduction (Anechoic) are consistently rated lower than the compensated cases (WY, WYX, WYXZ, WYXZR, WYZ) across all instruments, except for the noisy speech recording in the church. Additionally, the results show that the compensated direct signal (VBAP) achieves notably better-quality ratings than ConAmb.

leads to noticeable improvement. In particular, the WYX case achieves mean scores approaching 80%. For statistical analysis, pairwise comparisons were evaluated using two-tailed paired t tests, and p values were corrected for multiple comparisons using the Holm–Bonferroni method. For the subject variations shown in the lower left panel of Fig. 6, the statistical difference between the WYX and WY cases in the theater is not significant [$t(13) = 1.93, p = 0.14$], whereas in the church, the difference is significant [$t(13) = 5.98, p < 0.001$]. For the WYZ and WY cases, the ratings do not show significant differences in the theater [$t(13) = 0.61, p = 1$], but show significant difference in the church [$t(13) = 3.39, p = 0.01$]. The WYXZ case, also referred to as the B-format, does not show a significant improvement compared to the WYX case in either the theater [$t(13) = -0.26, p = 1$] or the church [$t(13) = -2.02, p = 0.24$]. Similarly, the compensated 4th-order Ambisonics case (WYXZR) does not show significant improvement over the WYXZ case in

the theater [$t(13) = -1.35, p = 0.60$] or the church [$t(13) = -1.53, p = 0.45$]. These results suggest that, within our approach, using just the WY channels along with the X (or possibly Z) channel is sufficient to achieve high-quality audio reproduction.

In the second part of the headphone evaluation, instead of using simulated rendering, the filtered audio files were physically played through a 50-loudspeaker array and recorded using a dummy head positioned at the center of the array. This experiment is important for two main reasons. First, it involves real reproduction, allowing for a more accurate comparison by capturing the complete chain of recording, processing, and playback without any simulation. Second, it enables an assessment of the method's robustness under realistic conditions. The robustness issue relates to two factors: (1) the displacement of the dummy head during real rendering compared to its original position during the dummy head recordings and (2) changes in the room

FIG. 7. Results from the second part of the headphone experiment using real audio playback in the loudspeaker lab. This experiment evaluates the robustness of the method, taking into account factors such as dummy head displacement and changes in the room environment over several months. While the overall trend is similar to that observed in the first headphone experiment (Fig. 6), some differences emerge due to ambient noise, particularly for the snare drum in the theater, where only the WYX case among the compensated methods outperforms VBAP. In the church, the lower scores for real speech reproduction reflect the impact of colored noise introduced during the processing stage, with only the WYXZ and WYXZR cases achieving scores comparable to VBAP and conventional Ambisonics (ConAmb). Increasing the number of channels helps reduce the effect of this noise, with the WYXZR case showing the most noticeable improvement.

environment between the two measurement sessions, which were conducted a few months apart. The results of this experiment are presented in Fig. 7.

Since the second headphone experiment does not involve simulation, the anechoic condition is excluded from this part of the evaluation. For individual instruments, the overall scoring trends are similar to those observed in the first part of the evaluation. All compensated cases, including WY, WYX, WYXZ, WYXZR, and WYZ, as well as the VBAP case, receive higher scores than the ConAmb case. The main difference between the first and second headphone experiments lies in the ambient noise level. In the second experiment, the ambient noise is audible at normal signal levels, which was not the case in the first part of the headphone experiment. Since the BRIR recordings of the loudspeaker array used in the first headphone experiment were conducted with a high SNR, ambient noise had a negligible impact on the quality of the main signal. There are two noticeable differences compared to the first headphone

experiment. First, for the snare drum in the theater, only the WYX case among the compensated cases achieved a higher mean score than VBAP. The snare drum, as an impulsive instrument with a broader frequency spectrum than the others, may reveal limitations in robustness across the full frequency range and may also be affected by the presence of ambient noise. The second major difference concerns the reproduction of real speech in the church. In the second headphone experiment, the scores for the compensated cases were significantly lower. In this context, only the WYXZ and WYXZR cases achieved scores comparable to those of the VBAP and ConAmb cases. This suggests that the colored noise introduced during the processing stage had a greater impact on perceived quality than the benefits offered by room compensation. As the number of reproduction channels increases, the influence of noise is progressively reduced. This reduction in noise is due to the spatial summation effect at the center of the array, particularly evident in the compensated WYXZR and ConAmb cases, where all

Ambisonics channels are utilized in the rendering process. These findings indicate that under conditions of low signal levels, such as speech in church, the influence of microphone and ambient noise becomes more pronounced, which can reduce the effectiveness of this approach. In such cases, the highest perceived quality is achieved with the VBAP method, which effectively attenuates recording noise through beamforming. For both subject and instrument variations shown in the two lower panels, the quality improvements in the compensated cases are statistically significant compared to the ConAmb case. Statistical analysis was conducted for instrument variations to compare the compensated cases. The differences between the WYX and WY cases in the theater [$t(13) = 3.34, p < 0.05$] and in the church [$t(13) = 3.34, p < 0.05$] are significant. The differences between the WYZ and WY cases are not significant in either the theater [$t(13) = 1.82, p = 0.09$] or the church [$t(13) = 0.29, p = 0.77$]. The WYXZ case show a significant difference in quality compared to the WYX case in either the theater [$t(13) = -2.52, p < 0.05$] or the church [$t(13) = 2.87, p < 0.05$]. Similarly, significant difference is observed between the WYXZR and WYXZ cases in the theater [$t(13) = 2.87, p < 0.05$] and the church [$t(13) = -2.54, p < 0.05$]. Considering the results from both headphone experiments, this suggests that within our approach, the WYX configuration, comprising the omnidirectional (W) and the two horizontal dipole (X and Y) channels, and also the B-format using WYXZ channels are well suited to achieve the highest attainable perceptual quality.

2. Loudspeaker evaluation

For these experiments, participants were seated at the center of the loudspeaker array and asked to rate the stimuli played through the loudspeakers. The evaluation followed a MUSHRA-like procedure without a hidden reference. The headphone reproduction was used as the explicit reference: Listeners were first presented with the binaural reference via headphones and could then remove the headphones at any time to evaluate the same signals reproduced by the loudspeaker array, switching freely between the headphone and loudspeaker playback. The headphone condition provided a stable and reproducible baseline, giving listeners a consistent clue as to how the stimuli should appear spatially and timbrally. Participants were encouraged to slightly move or rotate their heads during the experiment, allowing the robustness of the methods to be evaluated under natural listening conditions. The loudspeaker evaluation was conducted across three sessions: general quality assessment in the first session, timbral assessment in the second, and spatial naturalness in the third. The results of the general quality assessment are shown in Fig. 8. The general trend of improvement for the compensated cases is consistent with the results from the headphone evaluation. However, there are some notable differences. In the headphone experiment, particularly in its first part, the scores for direct VBAP rendering were generally higher than those for ConAmb.

In contrast, for the loudspeaker experiment, the scores for VBAP and ConAmb were, on average, very close to each other in both the theater [$t(13) = 1.73, p = 0.31$] and the church [$t(13) = 1.12, p = 0.56$]. This suggests that the headphone evaluation does not fully capture certain aspects of real loudspeaker reproduction.

Overall, the WYX and WYXZ cases achieve the highest scores. Adding higher-order channels (WYXZR) reduced quality in the theater, likely due to limitations arising from the specific loudspeaker layout and room interaction. Thus, within our playback setup and program material, three or four channels were sufficient to match the reference in terms of the reverberation and timbre related attributes evaluated. Previous work by Engel *et al.* (2019), showed that 1st-order Ambisonics is sufficient for diffuse late reverberation under binaural headphone reproduction. For loudspeaker playback, however, spatial resolution requirements can be higher, as indicated by Frank *et al.* (2025), particularly under anisotropic conditions or when the direct sound is absent. In our setup, the presence of a strong direct sound component, the compensated and largely isotropic reverberant field, and the dense 50-loudspeaker arrangement resulted in no perceptually relevant differences between 1st-order and higher-order rendering of the late reverberation.

Another interesting finding relates to the scoring of the noisy speech recording in the church. Unlike in the headphone evaluation, participants gave higher scores to the compensated signals, particularly in the WYX and WYXZ cases. This indicates that the presence of ambient noise in the recordings had a greater impact during the headphone evaluation compared to the loudspeaker evaluation.

In both rooms, the highest mean scores were observed for the WYX and WYXZ cases. This is particularly evident in the theater for the snare drum, which has the broadest frequency spectrum among the tested instruments. For subject variations, the difference between the WYX and WY cases in the theater [$t(13) = 2.36, p = 0.11$] is not statistically significant, whereas in the church [$t(13) = 3.10, p < 0.05$], it is significant. Furthermore, the differences between the WYZ and WY cases are not significant in either room [$t(13) = 1.36, p = 0.38$ in the theater; $t(13) = 1.70, p = 0.34$ in the church]. The same holds true when comparing the WYXZ and WYX cases, with no significant difference observed in the theater [$t(13) = -0.04, p = 0.97$] or the church [$t(13) = 0.29, p = 0.78$]. Interestingly, however, the difference between the WYXZR and WYXZ cases is statistically significant in the theater [$t(13) = -3.10, p < 0.05$]. In this case, adding all Ambisonics channels to the B-format results in a decrease in quality. This occurs because HOA components (Ambisonics orders between 2 and 4) are not well controlled: at low frequencies due to high noise levels and at high frequencies due to the very small size of the sweet spot. However, in the church, no significant difference was observed between the WYXZR and WYXZ cases [$t(13) = -1.86, p = 0.32$]. This suggests that using only three Ambisonics channels, one omnidirectional (W) and two horizontal dipoles (X and Y), is sufficient for rendering reverberant sound. Including all

FIG. 8. Comparison of quality in the loudspeaker evaluations. While the overall trends are similar to those observed in the headphone evaluation, some differences are evident. In particular, the noisy recording in the church receives higher scores compared to the headphone evaluation. ConAmb, conventional Ambisonics.

Ambisonics channels does not lead to improved quality in the rendered audio.

The second loudspeaker experiment focuses on spectral or timbral similarity. According to ITU-R BS.2399-0 (ITU, 2017), the term that more precisely describes this evaluation is “full,” which refers to the overall timbral impression encompassing both low- and high-frequency content. As in the first loudspeaker experiment, participants were allowed to listen to the reference audio via headphones and were permitted to move and rotate their heads during this session. The results of the timbre experiment are shown in Fig. 9. When participants were asked to evaluate based on timbre, the compensated VBAP method received significantly higher mean scores than the ConAmb case. This difference was statistically significant in both the theater [$t(13) = 3.63, p < 0.01$] and the church [$t(13) = 3.16, p < 0.05$]. This contrasts with the general quality evaluation, where listeners gave nearly identical scores to VBAP and ConAmb. Based on the subject and instrument variation data presented in the lower panels, the WYX case in the theater and the WYXZ case in the church achieved the highest mean scores. However, the differences between WYXZ and WYX cases

were not statistically significant in either the theater [$t(13) = -1.55, p = 0.55$] or the church [$t(13) = 1.68, p = 0.22$]. Similarly, no significant differences were found between WYX and WY cases in the theater [$t(13) = 1.13, p = 0.60$] or the church [$t(13) = 0.41, p = 0.69$]. These results indicate that adding more Ambisonics channels does not substantially affect timbral perception.

Furthermore, similar to the general loudspeaker evaluation, the inclusion of all Ambisonics channels does not lead to an improvement in quality and may, in some cases, result in a decline. The difference between WYXZR and WYXZ cases in the theater was not significant [$t(13) = -0.53, p = 0.43$], but in the church, it was significant [$t(13) = -2.75, p < 0.05$]. In summary, the results of the timbre evaluation, like those of the general quality experiment, suggest that increasing the number of Ambisonics channels does not lead to a noticeable improvement in perceived audio quality.

In the third session of the loudspeaker experiment, participants assessed the spatial naturalness of the stimuli. They evaluated how naturally spacious each stimulus sounded and how effectively it conveyed the sense of presence within the original acoustic environment, assigning higher scores to

FIG. 9. Results of the timbral comparison evaluation in both the theater and church environments. The compensated VBAP method yielded higher mean scores than conventional Ambisonics (ConAmb). On average, the WYX case performed best in the theater, while the WYXZ case showed the highest performance in the church. The findings suggest that adding additional Ambisonics channels does not significantly enhance timbral quality and may, in some cases, lead to a reduction in overall perceived quality.

stimuli exhibiting superior performance in these perceptual attributes. As in previous sessions, participants were allowed to freely move and rotate their heads during the evaluation. The results obtained from the spatial naturalness evaluation are depicted in Fig. 10. The main difference compared to the timbral evaluation in Fig. 9 relates to the scores of the VBAP and ConAmb conditions. In the lower panels of Fig. 10, the mean scores of ConAmb exceed those of the compensated VBAP. This result is generally expected since participants can readily perceive that signals reproduced using only VBAP sound drier compared to other stimuli. The difference between VBAP and ConAmb in the church environment is statistically significant [$t(13) = -2.75, p < 0.05$], whereas in the theater, this difference is not significant [$t(13) = -1.42, p = 0.18$]. This finding can be explained by the lower reverberation time in the theater, which reduces the influence of reverberant characteristics on perceived reproduction quality. For the theater, no significant differences are found among the other conditions regarding spatial naturalness. Interestingly, the WYXZR case in the theater shows similar mean scores to the WYX, WYXZ, and

WYZ cases when evaluating spatial naturalness. In the church environment, the difference between the WYX and WY cases is statistically significant [$t(13) = 3.34, p < 0.05$]. Furthermore, the WYZ case generally achieves lower mean scores compared to the WYX case. This outcome is attributed to participants primarily performing head movements in the horizontal rather than vertical plane, making the presence of the “X” pattern critical for robustness in horizontal localization. Adding additional Ambisonics channels does not notably enhance the perceived quality; for instance, the difference between WYX and WYXZ in church is not significant [$t(13) = -0.14, p = 0.89$]. These results confirm, as in previous experiments, that the WYX condition offers an optimal compromise between perceived quality and the number of channels required.

VI. DISCUSSION

In this study, we proposed a perceptually motivated recording and reproduction approach based on Ambisonics. The method not only compensates for the acoustics of the

FIG. 10. Results of the spatial naturalness evaluation for the theater and church environments. Participants assessed stimuli based on how effectively each condition conveyed the impression of being present in the original room while freely moving and rotating their heads. The evaluation also examined the robustness of the reproduction methods. Unlike the timbral evaluation, conventional Ambisonics (ConAmb) scored higher than compensated VBAP in terms of spatial naturalness, mainly due to the perceived dryness of VBAP reproduction. In the theater, no significant differences were found among the compensated conditions. In the church environment, the WYXZR case exhibited higher spatial naturalness scores than other compensated cases, except for the WYX case, which achieved the highest scores overall.

playback room but also implicitly addresses the spectral shaping required for conventional 4th-order simulated Ambisonics reproduction. Rather than aiming for a strictly physical reconstruction of the original sound field, the proposed scheme focuses on perceptually salient features, namely directional cues, energy distribution, spatial diffuseness, and reverberation characteristics.

For the recordings, we employed the Eigenmike EM32 microphone array (mh acoustics, 2023), which provides 4th-order Ambisonics signals through SH decomposition with radial filter compensation. For reproduction, a loudspeaker array with 50 loudspeakers arranged on a Lebedev grid was used, providing good orthonormality of SH up to 5th order (Lecomte *et al.*, 2016). This ensured that the reproduction stage had sufficient angular resolution to evaluate different Ambisonics orders and the proposed compensation scheme.

The direct sound was rendered using VBAP (Pulkki, 1997) in combination with beamforming, thereby preserving accurate directional cues. The reverberant sound field was

reproduced using Ambisonics at different channel configurations, including 4th order (25 channels), complete 1st order (WYXZ), and truncated versions (WY, WYX, WYZ). Both direct and reverberant signals were preprocessed using frequency-dependent mixing coefficients and energy compensation gains within a Gammatone filterbank framework. These parameters were optimized by comparing BRIRs from the recording and playback rooms, aiming to match perceptually relevant features at the listening position.

Listening experiments consistently demonstrated that compensated signals outperformed conventional Ambisonics reproduction in terms of timbre, spatial quality, and overall listener preference. Importantly, improvements were observed not only over uncompensated Ambisonics but also over simulated reproductions in anechoic conditions. This indicates that raw Ambisonics recordings are insufficient for high-quality reproduction unless equalized, consistent with findings by Favrot and Buchholz (2010), Zotter and Frank (2019), and Pfanzagl-Cardone (2023). An

additional strength of our approach is that it jointly compensates for both the playback room acoustics and spectral imbalances in the Ambisonics signals.

The loudspeaker experiments confirmed robustness against listener head rotations and moderate positional displacements from the sweet spot. The method was particularly effective for real recordings of piano, violin, and voice in the theater environment, despite mismatches between the optimization scenario (loudspeaker-based RIRs) and real instrument recordings with extended source width. These results underline the effectiveness of the energy-based compensation strategy.

A key outcome of this study is that relatively few Ambisonics channels are sufficient for rendering the reverberant sound field when combined with the proposed compensation. Previous work has demonstrated that the IC at the array center can already be controlled using only the W and Y channels (Fallah and van de Par, 2020). The W channel provides an omnidirectional, in-phase signal, while the Y channel produces a dipole pattern aligned with the interaural axis, generating out-of-phase components between the ears; a weighted combination can therefore reproduce the desired IC. Consistent with this, our results show that adding Ambisonics channels improves perceptual quality and robustness from WY to WYX, while WYXZ yielded very similar results to WYX without providing a clear additional benefit. Despite the reduced channel count, both WYX and WYXZ required far fewer signals than conventional 4th-order (25-channel) reproduction, and employing the full 4th-order set (WYXZR) did not yield consistent improvements over WYX/WYXZ. Compared to conventional 4th-order Ambisonics, which requires 25 channels, this represents a substantial reduction in storage and data transmission requirements. In our setup, the late reverberant energy could be rendered accurately with lower Ambisonics orders. Engel *et al.* (2019) have shown that 1st-order Ambisonics is sufficient for diffuse late reverberation under binaural reproduction, whereas Frank *et al.* (2025) reported that loudspeaker playback may require higher orders, especially when the direct sound is absent or the reverberation is anisotropic. In our case, the presence of a strong direct sound, the compensated and largely isotropic reverberant field, and the dense 50 loudspeaker array allowed 1st-order reproduction to match the perceptual performance of higher orders. It should be noted that all Eigenmike channels were still used for beamforming of the direct sound to ensure accurate localization cues.

Compared to our earlier work (Fallah *et al.*, 2024), which examined different channel reductions only in headphone listening tests, the present study extends the evaluation to robustness against positional displacements and changes in room conditions (e.g., movement of chairs or other objects), as well as robustness to head movement and rotation in the loudspeaker listening experiments.

There are still some constraints to consider. First, the T_{30} of the playback room should be lower than, or at most similar to, that of the recording room. This condition is

typically met in practice: for instance, when concerts recorded in reverberant halls are reproduced in living rooms or studios. Second, the optimization relies on having RIRs from the recording environment. While experiments with real instruments suggest that rough RIR estimates may already suffice, further systematic evaluation is needed.

The optimization was conducted using binaural signals recorded with an artificial head at the central listening position, consistent with common practice in Ambisonics evaluation, where the array center serves as the reference. While this approach is position-specific, our listening experiment demonstrated that the method is robust against small head movements and rotations. The resulting sweet spot was sufficiently large to permit natural listener movements without perceptual degradation. To address wider spatial coverage, strategies such as multi-position optimization or perceptual spatial averaging represent promising extensions for future work.

The present study has demonstrated the feasibility of optimizing reverberant recordings for reproduction in another reverberant environment under the assumption of a single source with known direction. While this restriction was necessary to ensure tractability, future research will focus on extending the approach to multi-source scenarios. In particular, strategies for recording and rendering multiple sources will be explored, with the goal of addressing DOA estimation challenges and mitigating potential time-frequency switching artifacts.

Overall, this work introduces a practical framework that compensates for both recording- and playback-related limitations. The results demonstrate that a perceptually guided strategy, using only a few Ambisonics channels for the reverberant field in combination with VBAP for the direct sound, can achieve higher quality and robustness than conventional HOA rendering.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study introduced a perceptually motivated approach for compensating the influence of the reproduction room on Ambisonics recordings reproduced in reverberant environments. By integrating compensated direct sound rendered with VBAP and applying frequency-dependent correction to the reverberant field, the method successfully preserved accurate directional cues while improving timbre, spatial quality, and overall listener preference as compared to using no compensation. Listening experiments with both headphones and loudspeakers showed consistent improvements compared to both conventional in-room Ambisonics reproduction and the simulated anechoic reproduction condition.

A key outcome is that relatively few Ambisonics channels are sufficient for rendering reverberation when combined with the proposed compensation. Truncated 1st-order configurations such as WYX provided perceptual performance comparable to or better than that of full 4th-order reproduction, consistent with the view that late reverberant

energy is predominantly of low directional order. At the same time, robustness against positional displacements, changes in room conditions, and listener head movements and rotation were demonstrated, highlighting the practical reliability of the method.

In the current study, the direct and reverberant components were explicitly handled, while early reflections were not addressed. Future work will therefore consider the separate treatment of early and diffuse sound fields. Furthermore, this study focused exclusively on single-source recording and reproduction; future research will extend the method to accommodate multiple simultaneous sound sources.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank the two reviewers for their helpful comments. This work is funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft [DFG (German Research Foundation)]: Project ID No. 352015383-SFB 1330 C2. The AI-based tool ChatGPT (OpenAI, San Francisco, CA) was used to assist with language editing during the preparation of the manuscript.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Ethics Approval

The listening tests conducted in this study were approved by the appropriate ethics committee at Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, and all participants provided informed consent in accordance with institutional guidelines.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. Audio examples, simulation scripts, and evaluation materials used in the listening tests can be shared for academic research purposes.

Ahrens, J., and Spors, S. (2009). "An analytical approach to sound field reproduction with a movable sweet spot using circular distributions of loudspeakers," in *2009 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*, Taipei, Taiwan (IEEE, New York), pp. 273–276.

Ando, Y. (1985). "Prediction of subjective preference in concert halls," in *Concert Hall Acoustics* (Springer, New York), pp. 70–88.

Arfken, G. B., Weber, H. J., and Harris, F. E. (2011). *Mathematical Methods for Physicists: A Comprehensive Guide* (Academic Press, New York).

Bäumer, T.-J., van de Par, S., and Fallah, A. (2025). "Comparative evaluation of room compensation approaches in Ambisonics reproduction," in *DAGA 2025*, Copenhagen, Denmark (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Akustik e.V., Berlin, Germany), pp. 1556–1559.

Berkhout, A. J. (1988). "A holographic approach to acoustic control," *J. Audio Eng. Soc.* **36**, 977–995.

Betlehem, T., and Abhayapala, T. D. (2005). "Theory and design of sound field reproduction in reverberant rooms," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **117**, 2100–2111.

Blauert, J. (1997). *Spatial Hearing: The Psychophysics of Human Sound Localization* (MIT Press, Cambridge, MA).

Bradley, J. S., and Soulodre, G. A. (1995). "Objective measures of listener envelopment," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **98**, 2590–2597.

Breebaart, J., Hotho, G., Koppens, J., Schuijers, E., Oomen, W., and van de Par, S. (2007). "Background, concept, and architecture for the recent MPEG surround standard on multichannel audio compression," *J. Audio Eng. Soc.* **55**, 331–351.

Breebaart, J., van de Par, S., Kohlrausch, A., and Schuijers, E. (2005). "Parametric coding of stereo audio," *EURASIP J. Adv. Signal Process.* **2005**, 1–18.

Brinkmann, F., and Weinzierl, S. (2017). "AKtools—An open software toolbox for signal acquisition, processing, and inspection in acoustics," in *AES Berlin 2017*, Berlin, Germany (Audio Engineering Society, New York).

Daniel, J. (2000). "Représentation de champs acoustiques, application à la transmission et à la reproduction de scènes sonores complexes dans un contexte multimédia" ("Representation of acoustic fields, with applications to the transmission and reproduction of complex sound scenes in a multimedia context)," Ph.D. thesis, l'Université Paris 6, Paris, France.

Engel, I., Henry, C., Garí, S. V. A., Robinson, P. W., Poirier-Quinot, D., and Picinali, L. (2019). "Perceptual comparison of Ambisonics-based reverberation methods in binaural listening," in *EAA Spatial Audio Signal Processing Symposium*, Paris, France (European Acoustics Association, Vaulx-en-Velin, France), pp. 121–126.

Fallah, A., Nakamura, S., and van de Par, S. (2024). "Exploring the impact of varying number of Ambisonic channels on a perceptually-based audio reproduction in reverberant rooms," in *DAGA 2024*, Hannover, Germany (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Akustik e.V., Berlin, Germany), pp. 1673–1675.

Fallah, A., and van de Par, S. (2020). "A new approach for rendering ambisonics recordings on loudspeakers in a reverberant environment," in *e-Forum Acusticum*, Lyon, France (European Acoustics Association, Madrid, Spain), pp. 2071–2077.

Faller, C., and Merimaa, J. (2004). "Source localization in complex listening situations: Selection of binaural cues based on interaural coherence," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **116**, 3075–3089.

Farina, A. (2000). *Simultaneous Measurement of Impulse Response and Distortion with a Swept-Sine Technique* (Audio Engineering Society, New York).

Favrot, S., and Buchholz, J. (2010). "Reproduction of nearby sound sources using high-order ambisonics: Implementation and evaluation," in *DAGA 2010*, Berlin, Germany (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Akustik e.V., Berlin, Germany), pp. 1063–1064.

Fielder, L. D. (2001). "Practical limits for room equalization," in *111th Audio Engineering Society Convention*, New York, NY (Audio Engineering Society, New York).

Frank, M., Gölles, L., and Riedel, S. (2025). "Spatial resolution of late reverberation in Ambisonic loudspeaker playback," in *DAGA 2025*, Copenhagen, Denmark (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Akustik e.V., Berlin, Germany), pp. 1560–1563.

Gauthier, P.-A., and Berry, A. (2006). "Adaptive wave field synthesis with independent radiation mode control for active sound field reproduction: Theory," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **119**, 2721–2737.

Gerzon, M. A. (1973). "Periphony: With-height sound reproduction," *J. Audio Eng. Soc.* **21**, 2–10.

GRAS (2025). "GRAS Sound and Vibration: KEMAR manikin," <https://www.grasacoustics.com/products/head-torso-simulators-kemar> (Last viewed December 18, 2025).

Grosse, J., and van de Par, S. (2015). "Perceptually accurate reproduction of recorded sound fields in a reverberant room using spatially distributed loudspeakers," *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Signal Process.* **9**, 867–880.

Haeussler, A., and van de Par, S. (2019). "Crispness, speech intelligibility, and coloration of reverberant recordings played back in another reverberant room (Room-In-Room)," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **145**(2), 931–944.

Hohmann, V. (2002). "Frequency analysis and synthesis using a Gammatone filterbank," *Acta Acust. united Acust.* **88**, 433–442.

Hold, C., Pulkki, V., Politis, A., and McCormack, L. (2024). "Compression of higher-order Ambisonic signals using directional audio coding," *IEEE/ACM Trans. Audio Speech Lang. Process.* **32**, 651–665.

ISO (2009). ISO3382-1:2009, "Acoustics—Measurement of room acoustic parameters—Part 1: Performance spaces" (International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland).

- ITU (2003). ITU-R BS.1534-1, *Method for the Subjective Assessment of Intermediate Quality Level of Coding Systems* (International Telecommunications Union, Geneva, Switzerland).
- ITU (2017). ITU-R BS.2399-0, *Methods for Selecting and Describing Attributes and Terms in the Preparation of Subjective Tests* (International Telecommunications Union, Geneva, Switzerland).
- Kuttruff, H. (2016). *Room Acoustics* (CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL).
- Lecomte, P., Gauthier, P.-A., Langrenne, C., Berry, A., and Garcia, A. (2016). "A fifty-node Lebedev grid and its applications to Ambisonics," *J. Audio Eng. Soc.* **64**, 868–881.
- Lecomte, P., Gauthier, P.-A., Langrenne, C., Berry, A., and Garcia, A. (2018). "Cancellation of room reflections over an extended area using Ambisonics," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **143**, 811–828.
- Litovsky, R. Y., Colburn, H. S., Yost, W. A., and Guzman, S. J. (1999). "The precedence effect," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **106**, 1633–1654.
- Mershon, D. H., and King, L. E. (1975). "Intensity and reverberation as factors in the auditory perception of egocentric distance," *Percept. Psychophys.* **18**, 409–415.
- mh acoustics (2023). "EM32 Eigenmike microphone array: Technical specifications and user manual," <https://mhacoustics.com/eigenmik> (Last viewed December 18, 2025).
- mh acoustics (2025). "EM64 Eigenmike microphone array: Technical specifications," <https://eigenmike.com/eigenmike-64> (Last viewed December 18, 2025).
- Moreau, S., Daniel, J., and Bertet, S. (2006). "3D sound field recording with higher order Ambisonics—Objective measurements and validation of a 4th order spherical microphone," in *AES 120th Convention*, Paris, France (Audio Engineering Society, New York), pp. 20–23.
- Mouchtaris, A., Reveliotis, P., and Kyriakakis, C. (2000). "Inverse filter design for immersive audio rendering over loudspeakers," *IEEE Trans. Multimedia* **2**, 77–87.
- Norcross, S. G., Soulodre, G. A., and Lavoie, M. C. (2004). "Subjective investigations of inverse filtering," *J. Audio Eng. Soc.* **52**, 1003–1028.
- Pfanzagl-Cardone, E. (2023). "HOA—Higher order Ambisonics (Eigenmike®)," in *The Art and Science of 3D Audio Recording* (Springer, New York), pp. 189–209.
- Poletti, M., Fazi, F., and Nelson, P. (2010). "Sound-field reproduction systems using fixed-directivity loudspeakers," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **127**, 3590–3601.
- Politis, A., Vilkamo, J., and Pulkki, V. (2015). "Sector-based parametric sound field reproduction in the spherical harmonic domain," *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Signal Process.* **9**, 852–866.
- Pulkki, V. (1997). "Virtual sound source positioning using vector base amplitude panning," *J. Audio Eng. Soc.* **45**, 456–466.
- Pulkki, V. (2007). "Spatial sound reproduction with directional audio coding," *J. Audio Eng. Soc.* **55**, 503–516.
- Rafaely, B. (2015). *Fundamentals of Spherical Array Processing* (Springer, New York).
- Schroeder, M. R. (1965). "New method of measuring reverberation time," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **37**, 1187–1188.
- Seraphim, H.-P. (1958). "Untersuchungen über die Unterschiedsschwelle exponentiellen Abklingens von Rauschbandimpulsen" ("Investigations on the difference threshold of exponential decay in band-limited noise impulses"), *Acta Acust. united Acust.* **8**, 280–284.
- Spors, S., Kuntz, A., and Rabenstein, R. (2003). "An approach to listening room compensation with wave field synthesis," in *AES 24th International Conference on Multichannel Audio* (Audio Engineering Society, New York), pp. 1–13.
- Stefanakis, N., Jacobsen, F., and Sarris, J. (2010). "Effort variation regularization in sound field reproduction," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **128**, 740–750.
- Stitt, P., Bertet, S., and van Walstijn, M. (2014). "Off-centre localisation performance of Ambisonics and HOA for large and small loudspeaker array radii," *Acta Acust. united Acust.* **100**, 937–944.
- van de Par, S., Kot, V., and Van Schijndel, N. (2005). "Scalable noise coder for parametric sound coding," in *AES 118th Convention*, Barcelona, Spain (Audio Engineering Society, New York), p. 699.
- Zhang, W., Khong, A. W., and Naylor, P. A. (2008). "Adaptive inverse filtering of room acoustics," in *2008 42nd Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers (IEEE)*, Pacific Grove, CA (IEEE, New York), pp. 788–792.
- Zotter, F., and Frank, M. (2012). "All-round Ambisonic panning and decoding," *J. Audio Eng. Soc.* **60**, 807–820.
- Zotter, F., and Frank, M. (2017). "Phantom source widening by filtered sound objects," in *142nd AES Convention*, Berlin Germany (Audio Engineering Society, New York).
- Zotter, F., and Frank, M. (2019). *Ambisonics: A Practical 3D Audio Theory for Recording, Studio Production, Sound Reinforcement, and Virtual Reality* (Springer Nature, Berlin, Germany).
- Zotter, F., Frank, M., and Haar, C. (2015). "Spherical microphone array equalization for Ambisonics," in *DAGA 2015 Nürnberg*, Nürnberg, Germany (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Akustik e.V., Berlin, Germany), pp. 486–489.
- Zuo, H., Abhayapala, T. D., and Samarasinghe, P. N. (2021). "3D Multizone soundfield reproduction in a reverberant environment using intensity matching method," in *ICASSP 2021-2021 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, Toronto, ON, Canada (IEEE, New York), pp. 416–420.